

‘Try or die’. The Travail of Migrants’

Is the new European Pact on Migration and Asylum adopted by the European Parliament and the Council of the EU in May 2024, in accordance with international human rights and the values of social justice?

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Declaration

Declaration of Authorship

I hereby declare that this thesis is my own work and that it has not been submitted anywhere for any award. Where other sources of information have been used, they have been acknowledged. ChatGPT was only accessed to double check for potential spelling errors, and to obtain an overview of past EU asylum policies as identified in a footnote.

Signed: *Conor Ryan*

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Elsewhere, I would also like to thank the people I interviewed or who completed my open-ended online questionnaire. Your comments were invaluable in providing “real world insights” as to how asylum claims are processed and the barriers people face in having their claims recognised.

Abstract

This dissertation sets out to examine whether the new *European Pact on Migration and Asylum* is in accordance with international human rights and the values of social justice. At present, there are fifty-six conflicts raging in ninety-two countries across the world, which is the highest recorded since Second World War (Global Peace Index, 2025). Human beings are increasingly being displaced either within their own country or forced to go abroad sometimes encountering horrific journeys across deserts and oceans only to not find a welcome at the other side. Instead, sometimes they are violently pushed back at border crossings by police, aided and abetted by agencies of the European Union (EU).

In undertaking my topic of choice, I wanted to expose not only the shortcoming of EU policies but also to highlight how interconnected the fate of people living in the ‘developing world’ are to our Western lifestyles and lingering colonial mindsets. The overthrow of the Libyan leader Colonel Gaddafi aided by the West and the abandonment of Afghanistan by NATO Allies has led to human right abuses for millions of people from these countries forcing them to seek asylum. In a twist of fate, hundreds of thousands of people, have fled and tried to gain sanctuary in “Fortress Europe” from these countries. ‘You Reap What You Sow’-Galatians 6:7-9.

However, it must also be pointed out that the vast majority of people granted refugee status are taken in by very poor neighbouring countries with the notable exception of Germany and Poland (Concern, 2025). It remains to be seen how the EU and the United Nations responds to the impacts of climate change in the coming decades for people who will try to seek asylum. International law would need to be amended to accommodate that eventuality but at present that seems an unlikely possibility in the current toxic political environment.

Glossary

AIDA	Asylum Information Database
AI	Artificial Intelligence
APR	Asylum Procedure Regulation
BBC	British Broadcasting Commission
DG	Directorate-General
EMN	European Migration Network
EPP	Europeans People's Party
EU	European Union
FRA	Fundamental Rights Agency
FOI	Freedom of Information
IPCC	The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate
IDMC	Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre
IHREC	Irish Human Rights and Equality Commission
IOM	International Organisation for Migration
IPA	International Protection Applicants
IPO	International Protection Office
IDMC	Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre
IPCC	International Panel on Climate Change
ECRE	European Council on Refugees and Exiles
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organisation
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
QR	Qualitative Research
MEP	Member of the European Parliament
SAR	Search and Rescue
SICAP	Social Inclusion and Community Activation Programme
TCN	Third Country Nationals
TPD	Temporary Protection Directive
UN	United Nations
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

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Chapter 1: Introduction.

Human rights are considered to be ‘*inherent, indivisible, independent, universal*’ and are set out in international law within the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights. Please refer to Appendix 1. Articles 1, 2, 3, 9, 13, 14 1, 14.2, 15 1, 15.2, 18, 20, 23, 25, and 29.1 are the most important in the context of my research aim. Collectively, these are the most discerning from a ‘moral and ethical’ perspective around how wealthier nations should respond to war, genocide, and the rapidly evolving climate crisis, resulting in millions of people trying to seek asylum worldwide. The aim and five research objectives of my dissertation are listed below.

Aim

Is the new European Pact on Migration and Asylum adopted by the European Parliament in April and by the Council of the EU in May 2024 in accordance with international human rights and the values of social justice?

Research Objectives

Review relevant literature from migration studies, social policy, and law to establish the social, economic, and legal context across the EU which informed the adoption of the Pact.

Apply a human rights and social justice lens, to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the Pact.

Analyse public opinion about the Pact through an examination of social media.

Illuminate the experiences of asylum seekers who have been or may potentially be affected by the Pact.

Create a series of recommendations, rooted in social justice principles, to improve the Pact and its operation.

The human right to asylum and non-refoulement as enshrined under Articles 18/33 of the 1951 Refugee Convention, are being openly questioned by politicians. An Independent Irish Senator recently suggested that there is “growing recognition that adherence to the outdated refugee conventions at the level of EU law and European Convention on Human Rights obligations in the face of international migration patterns is simply unsustainable politically, economically and socially” (McDowell, 2025). In some countries, politicians openly attack the judiciary if a court ruling does not go their way.

The right to assemble, free speech, and even the offer to help a human being who has washed up on a beach or drowning at sea are now under attack. One hundred and forty-two human rights activists have been criminalised for doing so (PIUCM, 2025a). Article 14 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) is particularly relevant in the context of my dissertation as powerful institutions are attempting to change the very concept of *asylum*. This states that: 1. *Everyone has the right to seek and to enjoy in other countries asylum from persecution.* 2. *This right may not be invoked in the case of prosecutions genuinely arising from non-political crimes or from acts contrary to the purposes and principles of the United Nations.*

The UDHR took three years for people from many different backgrounds and nations to craft and arrive at a common vision. According to the UN “it represents a powerful force for equality, social progress, justice, respect... and is a living testament to our shared humanity”. The actual Charter for the formation of the United Nations is celebrating its 80th year. Please click on this link to listen to more about the [Universal Declaration of Human Rights](#). Despite the many accusations that the UN is outmoded, never has never been a more important time for this institution to function more effectively. However, this is extremely difficult when five of its permanent members China, France, Russian Federation, the United Kingdom and the United States of America are at constant logger heads. Collectively, they represent just over two billion persons or a just quarter of the World’s entire population. Clearly, the permanent membership list needs to be extended to include other democratic nations who respect human rights law.

Chapter 2: Literature Review.

At present, there are fifty-six conflicts raging in ninety-two countries across the world, which is the highest recorded since Second World War (Global Peace Index, 2025). This calls into question issues around ‘*welfare and social justice*’. Sandel (2012, p.260) argues that there are three different approaches to justice. “One centres on maximising utility or welfare, the second that justice means respecting freedom of choice, and finally that justice involves cultivating virtue and reasoning about the common good”. In the context of achieving social justice for people impacted by natural disasters, climate change and wars, I would advocate in favour of the *third approach*.

Recently published data indicates that there are 83.4 million internally displacement people globally because of violence and conflict, which is an increase of 13.6 million in only two years (Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre, 2025). An additional 45.8 million people were internally displaced because of natural disasters such as cyclones. The Democratic Republic of Congo, Sudan, Palestine, Myanmar and the Lebanon reported the highest figures due to conflict and violence. By way of contrast, the United States, Philippines, India, China and Bangladesh reported the highest because of natural disasters. In terms of regional trends, Sub-Saharan Africa was the most affected (IDMC, 2024). The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change has identified Africa as the continent most vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. Northern Africa, which lies on the cusp of the European Union (EU), is expected to see a strong increase in temperatures and a decrease in precipitation, resulting in drier conditions (IPCC, pp. 21–52).

Map 1 Displaced by conflict and violence

Displaced by conflict and violence

73.5 million

Internally displaced people as a result of conflict and violence in 61 countries and territories as of 31 December 2024

↑ 10%

Increase in the number of people internally displaced by conflict and violence since 2023

Map 2 Displaced by disasters

Displaced by disasters

9.8 million

Internally displaced people as a result of disasters in 94 countries and territories as of 31 December 2024

↑ 29%

Increase in the number of people internally displaced by disasters since 2023

Source: Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre UNHCR

Definition of an asylum-seeker and refugee

The international definition of an asylum-seeker “*is someone who is seeking international protection. Their request for refugee status, or complementary protection status, has yet to be processed, or they may not yet have requested asylum, but they intend to do so*” (UNHCR, online, 2024). The United Nations (UN) also stipulates that it is a human right to seek asylum if someone is fleeing conflict or persecution and they should not be expelled or returned somewhere if their life would be placed in peril. The concept of *non-refoulement* is enshrined in the 1951 Refugee Convention and it important to highlight this in the context of the new EU Asylum and Migration Pact.

The 1951 Refugee Convention defines a refugee “*as someone who is unable or unwilling to return to their country of origin owing to a well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group, or political opinion*” (UNHCR, *ibid*). Once a person has been granted refugee status by the authorities this provides them with protection and certain legal rights. By way of contrast, an asylum seeker is someone who *wishes* to become recognised as a refugee but are waiting on their application to be processed by national authorities.

Intriguingly, the word *migrant is not defined in international law* (IOM, 2024). One could contend that the insertion of the word migrant into legislation and EU Directives was intentional and has increasingly led to confusion and uncertainty among the wider public about who actually is an economic migrant, asylum seeker and a refugee.¹ Words are important as will see further on in the analysis and findings chapter under the sub-heading *framing of migrants*.

The scale of asylum across the EU

According to the European Council on Refugees and Exiles “*asylum statistics are indispensable to any reasoned, evidence-led policy or debate on refugee protection*” (AIDA, 2015, p.1)). Figure 1 depicts a trend analysis of first-time asylum applicants to the EU from 2008 to 2024. As can be seen, the numbers fluctuate on an annual basis but there has been a clear upward trend over the past five years. Significant peaks have coincided with Syrians fleeing the Civil

War in 2015/2016 and more recently the invasion of Ukrainian territory by Russia in 2022 following its annexation of Crimea. It should be pointed out that not all asylum seekers are granted refugee status, and the rejection rate differs internationally and within the EU (Figure 3 overleaf). Data available from Eurostat demonstrates that the majority of asylum applications are rejected by the authorities. In 2024, the EU provided *protection status* to 437,900 asylum seekers. Of those, 42,4 percent were granted refugee status, 38.8 percent subsidiary protection and the remainder 18.8 percent humanitarian status. (Eurostat, 2024a). The primary beneficiaries to receive protection status last year were Syrians, Afghans and Venezuelans (Figure 2 overleaf).

Source: Eurostat

Figure 2-Asylum applicants granted refugee status in the EU, 2024

*Other refers to other citizenships with a share of less than 2%.
 Palestine*: This designation shall not be construed as recognition of a State of Palestine and is without prejudice to the individual positions of the Member States on this issue.
 Source: Eurostat - [migr_asydcfsta](#), [migr_asydcfina](#)

Figure 3-Distribution of first instance by outcome and country, 2024 (non-EU citizens, %)

Source: Eurostat - [migr_asydcfsta](#)

The views one hundred and seventy-eight *migration experts* were gathered via a *Delphi Survey*.ⁱⁱ Collectively they expected there to be an increase between 21-41 per cent in international migrants trying to arrive to Europe by 2030 compared to between 2008 and 2017 (Acostamadiedo et al, 2020). Therefore, given the certainty that people will continue to seek asylum in Europe but potentially on a much larger scale, one should examine how the EU intends to respond to that eventuality via the Pact. Before we can address this question however, one must briefly examine how the EU responded to accommodating millions of people who left their country of origin from 2015 onwards.

Overview of EU Asylum Policy ⁱⁱⁱ

Between 2015-2017, the EU introduced a new Relocation Mechanism with a target to relocate asylum seekers from Greece and Italy other member states. Only 34,000 were relocated out of a target of 160,00 due to non-compliance by some states such as Hungary and Poland. A voluntary resettlement programme for refugees outside the EU to Jordan, Lebanon and Turkey was also implemented. In 2016, the powers of Frontex who coordinate border controls and assist with processing asylum applications were enhanced. A new EU-Turkey deal was also struck the same year that saw a swap of Syrian refugees being accommodated in Turkey because in exchange for asylum seekers who were based in Greece for a sum of €6 billion. Elsewhere, similar bilateral agreements were struck with other countries through the EU Trust Fund for Africa and the Libya Cooperation. These funded projects that attempted to address the causes of migration and detention centres that were criticised by the late Pope Francis who compared them to **concentration camps** (Al Jazeera, 2020).

Efforts were also made by the various institutions of the EU to reform the Common European Asylum System.^{iv} These included the:

- Dublin Regulation III;
- Asylum Procedures Regulation;
- Qualification Regulation;
- Reception Conditions Directive.

However, attempts to amend the Dublin Regulation that stipulate that someone should only apply for asylum in their first country of entry proved unsuccessful. Finally, from 2020-2023,

a new Solidary and Migration Pact was discussed at length to bring about greater balance and responsibility among member states and the institutions. Proposals included mandatory solidarity Eurodac reform, Crisis and Screening Regulations. During this time period, new advanced surveillance techniques were deployed through facial recognition and drones and more pushbacks occurred in Poland. See figure 4 entitled “How EU Works” to garner a better understanding of how the various Institutions of the EU and external agencies all contribute to shape policy.

Figure 4 How the EU Works

Source: Jean Monnet Chair in EUGov

New EU Asylum and Migration Pact

After ten years of internal wrangling, the Council finally agreed a new EU Migrant and Asylum Pact in May 2024, herein called the *Pact*.^v The Pact is an international framework that sets out migrants and asylum seekers rules (European Council, 2024). It came into force in June of 2024, but it will not be fully operational until July 2026 after the legislation is transferred into national law across all Member States. Several templates that provide an overview of the Pact, which were extracted from the European Commission’s slick website page entitled ‘Managing migration responsibly’ are inserted into the Appendix B. The Pact *replaces* the Dublin Regulation and involves a “Solidarity Mechanism” whereby governments “can choose between different measures, such as financial assistance, relocation programmes, or logistical assistance” (Schug, 2024). The Dublin Regulation was originally adopted back in 2003, operated under an original assumption that people could expect to receive the same levels of protection irrespective of where they claimed asylum. However, over a period of time practices varied among member states.

Under the *Pact*, migrants who are *third-country nationals*^{vi} will be screened in a rapid manner to harmonise asylum procedures at external borders. Biometric data and an identity check will also be conducted. If their case is rejected by Immigration Officers, they will be returned to their country of origin. These activities will be conducted *close to the external borders* of the EU using a new method called the “fiction of non-entry”, which places people in transit zone or non-man’s land. Wealthier countries can also pay money into a joint EU fund as a way of avoiding receiving a certain number of refugees based on population. Despite its name, the Pact only deals only with those *irregular immigrants*^{vii} who claim asylum (Enriquez, 2024). The four pillars of the new migration and asylum policy include: *securing external borders, fast and efficient procedures, effective system of solidarity and responsibility* as well as embedding migration in *international partnership*. Please refer overleaf to view several infographics about the building blocks of the Pact and in Appendix B.

Figure 5 Implementation building blocks

Source: European Commission 2024.

Table 1 Legislative Acts

Table 1 The Pact's Ten Core Legislative Acts			
Title	Core Purpose	Date Act Applies	Ireland Opted-in?
Asylum Migration Management Regulation (AMMR)	Replace Dublin III Regulation and establish a new solidarity mechanism between Member States.	1 July 2026	Yes
Asylum Procedure Regulation (APR)	Establish a common EU-wide procedure for deciding on asylum applications.	12 June 2026	Yes
Recast (revised) Eurodac Regulation	Provide for the collection of additional biometric data from asylum seekers, including fingerprints from children aged six and above, and the creation of an asylum and migration database.	12 June 2026	Yes
Crisis and Force Majeure Regulation	Permit Member States to obtain derogations (temporary exemptions) from certain asylum obligations if they are in a crisis situation.	1 July 2026	Yes
Qualification Regulation	Provide for rights and obligations of beneficiaries of international protection.	1 July 2026	Yes
Recast Reception Conditions Directive	Harmonise reception conditions across the EU territory and require Member States to develop a contingency plan in case they receive a disproportionate number of arrivals.	12 June 2026	Yes
Resettlement Framework Regulation	Enhance safe and legal pathways to the EU for asylum seekers, and strengthen international partnerships with non-EU countries hosting large refugee populations.	June 2024	Yes
Regulation creating EU Agency for Asylum	Establish the EU Agency for Asylum (EUAA) to help Member States in applying EU asylum laws.	19 Jan 2022	Yes
Return Border Procedure Regulation	Establish a common return border procedure for returning unsuccessful applicants.	12 June 2026	No
Screening Regulation	Provide for uniform identity, health, vulnerability and security screening checks for certain categories of non-EU nationals.	12 June 2026	No

Colour code: Yellow = implementing legislation required by application date; Green = Act already applies; Red = Ireland has not opted-in, but national legislation will be aligned with Act, as far as possible

Source: Sweeney^{viii}, Senior Parliamentary Researcher Oireachtas

Reactions to the Pact

The Pact has been roundly criticised by Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) because it will lead to the ‘instrumentalisation’ of migrants (Amnesty International, 2023a) and the creation of a ‘legal liminal space’ (Schug, 2024). In this context alone, there is something deeply disturbing and about the Pact from a social justice perspective. During the Spanish Presidency of the Council of the European Union, a group of fifty NGOs sent an open letter (**Appendix H**) in the final days of the negotiations of the Pact (Jesuit Refugee Services, 2023). Within the letter entitled “Stand up for Human Rights, safety and dignity in the Migrant Pact” it states that:

the EU Pact on Migration and Asylum will mirror the failed approaches of the past and worsen their consequences...it will normalise the arbitrary use of immigration detention, including for children and families, increase racial profiling, use “crisis” procedures to enable pushbacks, and return individuals to so called “safe third countries” where they are at risk of violence, torture, and arbitrary imprisonment (Jesuit Refugee Services, 2023)

Human right breaches

The fears outlined by NGOs appear to be very well grounded after an international investigation undertaken by Lighthouse Reports. According to these investigative journalists', people have been randomly picked up off the street, transported to detention centres, forced to sign documents, denied legal aid and deported. These removal centres paid for by the EU that people are detained in, are overcrowded and unsanitary reminiscent of scenes from the movie *Midnight Express*. In some situations, the deportations have had horrendous outcomes people despite having legal papers to remain in Turkey as some were subsequently shot dead by the Taliban. This has been corroborated by over one hundred sources who spoke with more than a dozen diplomats. The reality is that such deportations are common, and the *EU is fully aware of these human right breaches*. Over twenty Freedom of Information requests submitted by Lighthouse Reports to various agencies have been rejected on account of *potentially damaging relations between the EU and Turkey*. The following quote is illustrative of one Syrian man interviewed by Lighthouse Reports who was detained by Turkish police.

I am at risk of losing my own life and my son's. I am a heart patient, and my son is a heart patient. I was going to buy household supplies when the Turkish police arrested me. In prison, we were severely tortured, beaten and insulted, they also detained us in a refrigerator for up to 12 hours. They forced us to sign voluntary deportation papers (Ahmed)

European leaders are fully aware of what is going on, they just don't want to get their hands dirty. The EU is indirectly facilitating forced returns. They subcontract human rights violations to third countries (Emma Sinclair, Human Rights Watch)

I will discuss the issue of *pushbacks* in the analysis and findings chapter.

The normalisation of pushbacks has become so pervasive that discussing it almost feels commonplace [and is] deeply concerning. It reflects a shift in how European borders are managed and raises serious questions about the erosion of longstanding principles of refugee protection (Itamar Mann, Associate Professor of Law at the University of Haifa)

Conclusions

The Council of the European Union passed the Temporary Protection Directive (TPD) for Ukrainian nationals in 2022 and has since extended it to 2027 for those escaping the war due to the Russian invasion of their country (European Council, 2025). The TPD offers immediate rights to Ukrainian nationals including access to labour market; access to housing; social welfare supports; and residency rights. Unaccompanied children also have rights to education and guardianship. However, one of the primary causes of human beings entering Europe by sea or land is via migratory routes from North Africa.

Unfortunately, the treatment of asylum seekers and *irregular migrants* across the EU is in stark contrast to the welcome afforded to Ukrainians. A different legal status applies to people who are migrating in search of a better life or displaced by *climate change and natural disasters*. Although they may be protected under human rights law, they do not necessarily have access to asylum (Brookings, 2023). It has been argued that in the context of climate change and disasters there are gaps in the international human rights architecture for people displaced (McAdam and Lippon, 2015).

Chapter 3: Theoretical Framework.

The Issue: The displacement of human beings to neighbouring countries or far away continents is not a modern phenomenon. Throughout history, people have been forced to leave their homeland due to natural disasters, war, ethnic cleansing, and more recently because of anthropogenic global warming.^{ix} The flight of Joseph and Mary along with the baby Jesus outlined in the Gospel of Matthew (Matthew 2:13-23) serves as a reminder that the Holy Family would be considered asylum seekers under Article 14 of the Geneva Convention.^x

This theoretical chapter draws on insights from a Social Justice Spirituality perspective to cast a lens on asylum, and how powerful institutions are responding to this complex public policy issue. In doing so, it will critique the response of the European Union through the lens of Walter Brueggemann's concept of "Royal Consciousness" and "Prophetic Consciousness" outlined in his seminal publication, 'The Prophetic Imagination'. Elsewhere, the chapter will also examine what the French philosopher Foucault previously said about confronting governments in relation to human rights and how he would have analysed the discourse within the new Pact. Finally, the influence of prophetic music figures and social movements, will be discussed in relation to how they may ultimately shape the public's perceptions and attitudes to people who seek asylum.

Royal Consciousness

Royal Consciousness refers to the ideology of dominant power structures that too often maintain control, suppress dissent, and create inequality, which Brueggemann examined during the time when Moses lived and the Exodus story. Such regimes are characterised by maintaining the status quo and stability at the expense of human dignity and social justice. It is possible to draw an analogy to the political responses adopted by the EU with the challenge of asylum. For many people, the EU has increasingly become a "self-serving achievement" and "an elaborate bureaucracy" (Bruggemann, 2001, pp. 23-24). This will become clearer when specific aspects of discourse included within the Pact are examined. I would contend that the "economics of affluence counters the economics of equality" as set out in Brueggemann's description of royal consciousness nowadays applies to the EU despite its protestations to the alternative.^{xi}

The bloc of twenty-seven countries could be accused of ‘becoming numb and displaying a lack of care and passion’ (Bruggeman, *ibid*) to the plight of people fleeing war, famine or escaping climate change in Africa. Since 2014, it has been estimated that 76,529 migrants are missing of which 32,440 have drowned trying to cross the Mediterranean Sea (IOM, 2025). Please click on [Spotify](#) link to learn more. It is as though Europe has collectively become static, indifferent, and numb to human suffering. The continuing implementation of flawed asylum policies adopted by the EU and non-engagement by countries such as Hungary (ECHR, 2025) may be further critiqued by reflecting on the thoughts of a leading German philosopher. Heidegger claimed that:

Not only in Germany, but Europe generally, we have lost, we have no clear, common, and simple relation to reality and to ourselves. That is the greatest problem facing the Western world and is one reason for the confusion of opinions between different things (Philosophy Overdose)

Map 3: Missing migrants

Source: IOM, 2024.

Foucauldian discourse analysis

A critical theorist Michel Foucault examined concepts such as power, knowledge, and discourse. He invented the term *governmentality* to describe how modern nation states rely not just on administrative practices to manage their citizens, but also through legislation transposed into nation law as a consequence of an EU Directive. In addition, Foucault explained how **neoliberal rationality** helped introduce concepts such as *biopower* and *biopolitics*, was disturbed by how discourse produced subjects and examined institutions of discipline. He would have had significant reservations about the emphasis on particular discourse included within the Pact. ‘In every society the production of discourse is at once controlled, selected, organised and redistributed by a number of procedures whose role is to ward off its powers and dangers, to gain mastery over its chance events, to erode its ponderous, formidable materiality’ (Foucault, 1981c, p.52).

Häkli, Kudžmaitė, and Kallio remind us that several studies have identified that the EU views migration as an existential threat and a problem that needs to be solved (Bialasiewicz, 2012; Jones & Johnson, 2016; Salvati, 2021). The following quote from an official document is indicative of this:

These [challenges] include an increasing proportion of applicants for international protection without genuine claims who are unlikely to receive protection in the EU with a resulting increased administrative burden and delays in granting protection for those in genuine need of protection as well as a persistent phenomenon of onward movement of migrants within the EU (European Commission, 2020, p.10).

Tellingly, the word asylum is sparsely referenced in the Pact compared to an *applicant* or *third country national* (See Table 2 in the analysis and findings chapter). This is significant because it has been claimed that:

The notion of exclusion is very important in Foucault's thinking ... we should think of a discourse as existing because of a complex set of practices ...and that discourse is associated with relations of power..... does not simply translate reality into language; rather discourse should be seen as a system which structures the way we perceive reality... as it constrains our perceptions (Mills, 2001, p. 54-55).

As such, Foucault would have argued that the Pact in effect differentiates between “deserving” and “undeserving” migrants even though the word migrant is not defined in international law (IOM, 2025a). Further to this, the use of invasive technology (Recast Eurodac Regulation) used to gather personal and sensitive data about people via biometric identification systems would have troubled him (Screening Regulation/Return Border Procedure Regulation). These activities will occur at detention centres on Europe’s external borders in North Africa. The European Border and Coast Guard Agency (Frontex) operates to patrol Europe’s land and sea borders and are therefore part of the wider infrastructure from a migration angle. This agency is governed by Regulation (EU 2019/1896) and is the EU’s first full uniformed law enforcement service that fights crime and plays a “crucial role in conducting border checks and registering *irregular migrants*” (Frontex, online, 2025). Foucault would proclaim that these agencies^{xii} are the new “institutions of discipline” akin to his ideas about prisons, which are part of the new “disciplinary apparatus” of the Pact who have significant powers of repatriation (Foucault, 1991).

Language and discourse produce *subjects*, and the Pact could further reinforce a growing misunderstanding by security personnel and the wider public between what is actually an asylum seeker and a migrant in “non-exclusion zones” (Article 6 Screening Regulation). Such categories are not neutral and according to leading scholars the *human frame analysis* “continually and selectively classifies migrants.... as a strategy used for organising and comparing people as data, which neglects the personhood of migrants (Häkli et al, 2024, p.6). Foucault would further argue that this *turn* in the EUs migration policy, reveals its broader strategy of regulating population movements via the categorisation of human beings into statistical cohorts that diverts people’s attention away from the true scale of asylum. The outsourcing of asylum processing to third countries including Morocco and Turkey is an explicit example of *externalisation strategy by the EU* and the politics of exclusion.

Elsewhere, the “mandatory solidarity” of the Pact that enables Member States either to accept asylum seekers onto its territory *or* fund their return would be further critiqued by Foucault as yet another example of the neoliberal agenda and the marketisation of human suffering. At face value, the “solidarity mechanism” whereby nations experiencing higher levels of migration can request help from other EU countries nations to take their fair share of migrants may be offset by wealthier nations who can fulfil their obligations by making a greater financial contribution to the “solidarity pool”. Alarming, the latest ‘Return Regulation’ proposal could see the

deportation of children from the EU (PICUM, 2025a). Foucault would undoubtedly have chastised it for this course of action. Evidence for this can be drawn from his insights about the Vietnamese boat people in the 1970s who fled persecution from the Communist government, where he made a strong case for human rights. Foucault pointed out^{xiii} that we are all international citizens and that there is an obligation on all of us to confront governments whose policies are regressive:

there exists an international citizenship which as such has its rights and duties, and which is obliged to stand up against all forms of abuse of power, no matter who commits them, no matter who are their victims and “it is a duty of this international citizenship to always confront the eyes and ears of governments with the human suffering for which it cannot truthfully be denied that they bear responsibility. It grounds an absolute right to stand up and to challenge those who hold power (Coombes, online, 2016)

Prophetic Consciousness

Although some might like to think that European Pillar of Social Rights (EPS, 2017) attempts to bring back a social dimension to the EU and reconnect with European citizens, there is no reference to asylum seekers and refugees in the pillar. Economic policy still appears to be the dominant consideration as set out under the Stability and Growth Pact with its set of fiscal rules. However, spirituality would contend that we are capable of self-transcendence to cut through the numbness, but the question is how. Brueggemann’s “Prophetic Consciousness” entails an *awareness of social injustices* and a *commitment to a more just world*. Prophets have an ability to critique power structures and inspire radical transformative action. Their expanded social consciousness is characterised by a commitment to truth, justice and the well-being of people including the marginalised and oppressed.

Artists as prophetic voices

For Brueggemann “in songs and poems comes the ultimate challenge to managed reality and its language and discourse. Brueggemann holds that only art “*is the universe of discourse in which energy is possible...and subversive art gives voice to the voiceless, exalts and includes the marginalized, and contradicts oppression through its language*” (Reyes, pp.98-101). Technology can alienate ourselves from others as “*daily distractions draw our eyes downward:*

toward our phones, our to-do lists, our immediate needs and wants. Amidst this onslaught of distractions, it is increasingly difficult to sustain focus on the big issues (climate change, nuclear war) that threaten our survival as a society and as a species....” (Braunstein, online, 2018).

At present, too many people are apathetic, not in touch with their emotions due to the *black mirror effect* and have little empathy towards the plight of asylum seekers. Nevertheless, a crisis of liminality might awaken the minds of the masses of and result in a counter-culture movement against the Pact. Given this tragic situation, one can legitimately ask whether “The arts” have the potential to transform public consciousness in the future. There is a possibility that a *new social movement* might arise in the future when enough Europeans discover how people are being treated in third countries, as progress on the United Nations Sustainable Goals falter due to rapid climate change in the coming decade.

Artists such as Creedence Clearwater Revival-Fortunate Son (1969), Marvin Gaye-What’s Going On (1971), Midnight Oil-Beds Are Burning (1987), Tracy Chapman-Talkin’ ‘bout Revolution (1998), and the Manic Street Preachers-The Everlasting (1998), have all embodied the prophetic tradition through their songs of protest (Milano, 2024). Music could therefore play a crucial role once again in offering a powerful medium for communicating social justice concerns and inspire collective action as it did during the anti-Vietnam war protests in the 1960s, and anti-apartheid marches in the 1980s.

The values of the EU are stated in the Lisbon Treaty and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. The latter outlines that “the EU is built on fundamental rights, democracy and the rule of law” (EUR-Lex, 2024).^{xiv} The demise of King Solomon’s empire should serve as a warning that the EU could crumble within due to greed and the desire for power as its population rapidly ages. This will cause significant problems for the provision of social care caused by an imbalance between the economically dependent and working population. The EU should remember that “all beings have equal and inalienable rights” ([UDHR,1948](#)) and reflect on the lyrics by the Welsh rock band, Manic Street Preachers in the song ‘[The Everlasting](#)’.

*The world is full of refugees
They’re just like you and just like me
But as a people we have a choice
To end the void with all its force*

Chapter 4: Methodology.

Overview

It has been claimed that “philosophers and social scientists share a common goal: to explore fundamental truths about ourselves and the nature of the world in which we live” (Benton and Craib, online, 2025). However, within the two distinct disciplines, the means about how we discover these truths are disputed. The following chapter will present different interpretive frameworks, ontological, epistemological, axiological and methodological beliefs. In doing so, it will provide a general overview the philosophy of the social sciences and discuss one qualitative research approach; namely *phenomenology* is more detail. Elsewhere, the chapter will also discuss the research problem, the research design, population and sample, procedures, data processing, quality and ethical assurance along with a summary.

Research Problem

Given that the overall aim of the dissertation is whether “*the new European Pact on Migration and Asylum adopted by the European Parliament in April and by the Council of the EU in May 2024 is in accordance with international human rights and the values of social justice?*”, the question arises as to what were the most appropriate method(s) to investigate this research problem.

Philosophical Underpinnings

Philosophical and interpretive frameworks are important considerations within the research process. All research is based on some underlying assumptions about what constitutes valid research and knowledge, and which research methods are appropriate. To conduct and/or evaluate quantitative/qualitative research, it is important to know what these assumptions are. Guba and Lincoln (1994) suggest that here are four underlying "paradigms" for research: positivism, post-positivism, critical theory, and constructivism. These include the nature of reality (ontology), how knowledge is known (epistemology), the acknowledgement of values in research (axiology) plus how research is conducted (methodology) (O'Brien, 2024). By way

of contrast, Orlikowski and Baroudi (1991), suggest three categories, based on the underlying research epistemology: positivist, interpretive and critical. Irrespective of whether there are three or four, there is considerable disagreement as to whether these research "paradigms" or underlying epistemologies are necessarily opposed or can be accommodated within the same study (Myers, 1997). Included in Appendix, G is a table that sets out various interpretative frameworks and their associated philosophical beliefs.

Methodology really concerns the process, procedures and principles applied to gain answers to a research problem identified by a researcher. Positivistic quantitative approaches are generally fixed, that might test a theory through a deductive approach and has its roots in the Enlightenment period (Bogdan and Taylor, 1975). In contrast, qualitative methodologies attempt to capture a more nuanced version of reality that is fluid and socially constructed, and generally more favoured by human/social scientists (Sloan and Bowe, 2014). Nevertheless, according to a duo of academics "in a strict sense there is no such thing as QR" (Conzon and Small, 2022, pp9).^{xv}

Research design

A qualitative research design was the primary methodology that I choose to initially apply to answer the research problem. The types of qualitative research involved one-to-one interviews, content analysis and narrative research. I agree with Dreher (1994, p293) when she states that 'providing a rationale for using a specific method should not be a treatise on the relative merits of phenomenology or logical positivism, but rather the clearest explanation possible for why the proposed strategy has the most potential for answering the specific research question and ultimately improving the practice on which the research question bears. Pragmatic factors such as resources, time and access were careful considerations. The priority of my research project was to primary collect non-numeric data with the ultimate goal of achieving a 'depth rather than a breath of understanding' (Coleman, 2007) and answer one of the core objectives: *Analyse public opinion about the Pact through an examination of social media.*

According to Creswell (2006, p.23), the "construction of meaning is a central human activity and that in phenomenological research, the structure of consciousness of lived experiences is explored with the goal of giving the reader an accurate understanding of the essential, invariant

structure (or essence) of an experience”. For the purposes of investigating my qualitative research problem, I chose a *social constructivism* approach specifically from a phenomenological angle because I wanted to arrive at a deeper meaning and shed more light on the complexities of social phenomena through rich, detailed data collection and analysis (O’Brien, *ibid*). The ontological, epidemiological, axiological and methodological beliefs associated with social constructivism are set out in Appendix G.

It is important to point out that there are different types of phenomenology informed by two diverse but not unrelated perspectives (Bowe and Sloan, *ibid*). The original version called *descriptive phenomenology* was espoused by Edmund Husserl while Martin Heidegger advocated an *interpretative/hermeneutic phenomenological approach*. Hegel was also one of the original proponents of phenomenology argued that “all reality was constructed by the mind, but the mind was not necessarily aware of it in a vast system he labelled the Absolute. In addition, he claimed that “according to Idealism, reality is not made up of things that exist outside our heads, but they exist *within* the mind (Jackson, pp. 10, 2017).

Husserl believed that through a descriptive phenomenological approach someone can transcend the phenomena and gain a bird’s eye perspective on the ‘essences discovered’ (Sloan and Bowe, *ibid*). Heidegger differed in his opinion however and believed that a philosopher or social scientist could not really remove themselves from the process of essence-identification because they co-existed with the phenomena and the essences. As a consequence, it is not necessary to “bracket off the narrative” [] gathered. I attempted to follow a *hermeneutic phenomenological approach* based on the data I gathered via interviews and documents.

Primary Field Research- Population and Sample

As the SETU Ethics Committee would not allow me interview asylum seekers, I had to rely instead on alternative means of gathering rich data sets. This had implications for the social research methods I choose to apply and sampling decisions to gain access to the key stakeholders plus which documents to download. As a consequence, my study only sought to elicit insights from human rights lawyers, journalists, university academics, Members of the European Parliament (MEPs), Non-Governmental Organisations who support asylum seekers, along with Irish government officials. I initially hoped that I could have relied on a

‘*snowballing method*’ of reaching research participants whereby a Gatekeeper might introduce me or suggest other potential research respondents to contact, but this never transpired. Instead, I wrote to thirty-five people/organisations via email, Express Post and occasionally by ringing them, to try and obtain a ‘*purposive sample*’ of respondents. This is in contrast to quantitative research that would be more likely to employ a probability sampling approach (Punch, 2005).

A list of eight draft questions was inserted into the ethics application template after conducting a literature review of documentation around the Pact and the challenges related to asylum. The draft questions were examined by my Research Methods module lecturer and amended based on the feedback received back. Some additional questions were inserted to the final version of the *interview schedule*, which was very open ended in nature and designed to allow for a process of interaction between the researcher and respondent.^{xvi}

Data Processing

All respondents were provided with an opportunity to attend either a digitally recorded *semi-structured interview* via Zoom or click on a link where the same questions were uploaded to an online survey platform called *SmartSurveys*. This licensed platform used to administer an online questionnaire through software was GDPR compliant. I familiarised myself with the data by reading over the transcripts. The narrative gathered was extracted verbatim into a word document for analysis informed by *thematic analysis approach*. It has maintained that “theme captures something important about the data in relation to the research question and represents some level of *patterned* response or meaning within the data set” (Bruan and Clarke, 2006, p.10).

Secondary Research

My literature review, findings, conclusions and policy proposals were directly informed by a heterogenous source of data sets. These included:

- Online newspaper and journal articles;
- NGO policy papers;
- Ten core legislative acts of the Pact;
- EU Directives;
- Statistics derived from official Irish/EU websites;

- YouTube uploads;
- Books about asylum seekers trying to reach Europe;
- Vignettes/Stories.

Although, the desk research process was time consuming, it was critical to informing the various stages of the overall dissertation. It was helpful in educating me about the true scale of asylum and drownings occurring, as well as the dark forces and actors that operate to reduce the numbers of asylum seekers arriving in Europe. In addition, it highlighted the contradictory stance of the European Union in offering extended special status recognition to Ukrainian nationals forced to flee their country but not to African's. The inclusion of *vignettes and stories* to illustrate the experiences of asylum seekers who could have been affected by european immigration policies was important in addressing one of the research objectives: *Illuminate the experiences of asylum seekers who have been or may potentially be affected by the Pact.*

Discourse Analysis

The interpretation of documents conducted by someone else known as qualitative context analysis is a key consideration. My secondary research was partially informed by a complex piece of *discourse analysis* conducted by leading academics. They analysed the discourse included in legislative acts through data analysis tools: Atla.ti and Voyant Tools (Hakli et al, 2023). They identified that the word asylum is only included fifty times in the Pact compared to an *applicant* which is inserted over six hundred times (See table 1). These also helped pinpoint that “non-exclusion zones” that are inserted to Article 6 Screening Regulation are not neutral categories.

Reflection on research approach taken

Although I attempted to carry out phenomenological approach based on open-ended interviews, it is important to stress that the overall project was broken down into distinct but connected stages from a literature review, fieldwork, data collection, and data analysis to dissertation production. In effect, a mixed research methodology was used. The long list of references that informed my secondary research is evidence that there is a level of authenticity, credibility and representativeness to the overall body of the dissertation. While reading a

document helps someone arrive at an understanding and access some form of reality, it still does have its limitations. It should be recognised that “documents have a distinctive ontological status, in that they form a separate reality” (Atkinson and Coffey, pp. 527). Because I also had to interpret the documents myself this is a form of double interpretation or hermeneutics.

Consent

Every safeguard was taken to ensure that the interviews proceeded in a calm and relaxed atmosphere. The most disappointing outcome was that I only gathered feedback from a small number of experts. However, this was not down to a lack of trying on my behalf. Please see appendices for a list of people and organisations contacted. Unfortunately, I only got to actually interview one individual because all other participants decided to complete the interview schedule via an online link. The one face-to-face interview that did take place was convivial and recorded on my phone as the individual rang me and choose not to do so via Zoom. All respondents completed a Consent Form, but they had to be followed up with to obtain them.

Reflexivity

Finally, one aspect I was very conscious of in advance of starting the research was my own potential bias and *reflexivity* as a White Irish Male. As has been made evident by others, notions of objectivity are really located in positivist epistemology...the point of reflexivity is to make your own political, theoretical and/or personal influences known to the reader so your conclusions and can be appraised in that context (Lazard and McEvoy, p 3-4). The overall aim of the dissertation was to cast a lens on the Pact *through a human rights inquiry and the values of social justice*. In that sense, one should acknowledge that it was not possible to be objective as a researcher when conducting my enquiry via a qualitative approach.

I had to select representative examples of men, women, undocumented migrants and minors to try and cover the various grounds for why someone might seek asylum from online sources and documents. Elsewhere, although information was drawn from mass-media outputs, I deliberately choose to minimise exposure to many *virtual documents* such as postings on message boards and forums, which too often contain racist comments by far-right activists. This is a form of bias in itself but was done so to avoid any potential negative feelings and reaction I could have encountered otherwise.

Chapter 5 Analysis and Findings

The following chapter is divided into sub-sections. It will examine:

- Why people have to seek asylum in another country;
- Qualitative responses to my interview schedule; ^{xvii}
- The opinions of ‘experts’ in the field of migration;
- Examine what investigative journalists have highlighted about migration responses external to the EU;
- Examine public opinion regarding the Pact via social media commentary.

Lived Experiences of Asylum Seekers

In this section, I have provided sample case studies to highlight why people seek asylum, which I have interpreted to make sense of their own lived experiences. This is in keeping with my phenomenological methodological approach. Please note, the majority of the qualitative quotes are inserted into the Appendices *and should be read in conjunction with my commentary*. The analysis and subsequent findings are also informed by:

- Statistics;
- Journalist interviews;
- Information extracted from previous research conducted by human rights organisations that support this very vulnerable group of people.

In doing so, it will demonstrate how asylum seekers have already been negatively affected by EU migration policies and how they could in the future when the Pact becomes operational after July 2025. Please refer to **Appendix D** to view all the qualitative narrative from asylum seekers. What follows in the next part are select quotes.

‘Try or die’

The *BBC Africa Eye* conducted an in-depth investigation into the world’s deadliest migration route from West Africa. The following quotes are extracted from an interview with a 40-year-old Senegalese male, who undertook an arduous and perilous journey from Africa to try to reach the Canary Islands in Spain. Ultimately, he was unsuccessful and was forced to return to Senegal when the boat he was being smuggled on experienced motor difficulties. Despite being exploited by traffickers ‘en route’ with few food or water provisions and suffering horrific injuries, he is committed to trying again. What is shocking and tragic about Mouhamed’s circumstances is his determination, knowing that he may never see his family again.

The boat guys have called me - they said I should get ready. I am asking you to pray for me - the time has come (Mouhamed Oulay)

Nobody knows what could happen to me in these waters. The evil spirits of the sea could kill me

The boat could capsize, killing everyone. If you fall into the water, what would you hold on to? The only possibility is death, but you have to take risks

The motor was heating up and the wind was so strong, some of the fishermen suggested we head to Morocco. But the captain refused. He said if we moved slowly, we’d be in Spain by 6am

Everyone started arguing and insulting each other. The captain gave in and turned back to Senegal

You will see people in the water who have died, but the boats keep going

There are a lot of us, we've filled the house. There are people from Mali and Guinea too. They take us in small boats of 10 to 15 people until we get to the big boat, then we leave

I did any job you can imagine, but things didn't get any better. If you don't have money, you don't matter. I am their only hope and I don't have money

I wish to go back and try again. Yes, honest to God, that is my belief. That is better for me. If I die, it is God's choice

Police and NGO

Every 45 minutes, a migrant dies trying to reach our beaches. This means trafficking mafias are increasingly becoming more powerful (Mr Clavijo, referencing data Spanish rights group Walking Borders)

The mafias that organise trips have realised that this is like drug trafficking, with little chance of being detected (Lieutenant Antonio Fuentes, Spain's Guardia Civil set up to tackle the smugglers)

Extreme poverty and climate change are forcing many asylum seekers to try and reach Europe from West Africa sometimes after attempting sea journeys or crossing land borders to reach North Africa. Along the way they may suffer horrendous violence and exploitation. Several of the above quotes are illustrative of the total disregard for human life smugglers have. They appear to only care about their own financial gain. Please click on the link [here](#) to learn more about Africa's deadliest migration route.

Unaccompanied Minors and Religious Persecution

In 2024, over a quarter of asylum seekers (234,670) who arrived in Europe were aged *less than* 18 years of age. 15.9 percent of these were unaccompanied minors and are in a very vulnerable position. In relation to unaccompanied minors' 31.8 percent were from Syria where a civil war raged for over a decade and 15.6 percent from Afghanistan (Eurostat, 2024). American and Allied forces abruptly left in 2021 and within a fortnight the Taliban had taken back over the country, Since then, human rights abuses on vast scale have occurred (Amnesty International, 2024a).

They tried to put us in the military [in Eretria] but we escaped. But the ones who didn't escape, they are still in the military. Almost everybody escaped, even the kids escape because they know their brothers' future, what will happen in the future. That's why they try to escape when they are kids (Unnamed, extract from book: My Fourth Time We Drowned, Journalist, Sally Hayden)

Although war is one of the largest contributory causes for people seeking asylum sometimes people have to flee because of *religious persecution* in their own country. According to Open Doors, 380 million Christians suffer elevated levels of persecution, and thousands are killed every year. The following first-hand account is just one example of how Christians are oppressed.^{xviii}

The day I decided to convert from Islam to Christianity, I lost everything that had been essential in my life up to that point. I lost the faith I grew up with. I lost my country and my community, where many people now wish me dead. But the most difficult to accept is that I lost my family. When my mother said, "I wish you died before telling me because for me you just died today," I felt my heart being crushed a thousand times. It was at this point that my mental health began to suffer. I left my country in July 2017 to save my own life. That was when I stopped feeling (Mouhamed).

Source: YOUNGMINDS

Undocumented Migrants

Although hundreds of thousands of asylum seekers manage to reach Europe each year, many do so without having a passport or identification. This can occur because they have to flee their homeland in an emergency situation (e.g. ethnic cleansing or the sudden onset of a new conflict). After arriving in Europe and being denied asylum by the authorities at their point of entry, they may continue on foot to another European country. They do so in the hope of achieving a more positive outcome about their application elsewhere. However, very often this does not occur, and they find themselves living in a state of limbo unable to access essential services, and end of living in a state of destitution. They live in constant fear of being deported and often tragically, many take their own lives.^{xix}

I left my country in 2009, driven by political tensions. I undertook a journey to Belgium, hoping to find a better life and protection. Once I arrived here, I realised that life without papers is extremely difficult. I don't have legal status, which means I have to work in precarious jobs, often poorly paid. I do cleaning and construction work, but I'm often exploited and have no rights. Finding stable housing is a real challenge; I often live in shared flats, sometimes in unsanitary conditions. And now I'm looking for a squat because I can no longer pay. I've tried to regularise my situation by submitting several applications, but they were all rejected. This leaves me in a constant state of uncertainty. Psychologically, it's a heavy burden. I feel a deep sense of isolation and anxiety. I dream of finding a solution to live with dignity here and, above all, to be able to start a family in Belgium (40-year-old man from Guinea, interviewed in Brussels)

Gender Based Violence

The United Nations has reported that there are now sixty million women and girls who have been displaced because of gender based violence. Sexual violence against women has increased by sixty per cent in the last year alone. Even more shockingly, it has been estimated that ninety per cent of all women and girls that have followed the Mediterranean route from parts of Africa have been raped. The perpetrators are reportedly armed gangs, smugglers and traffickers (UN, 2024). The women who try and seek asylum in Europe must recount their ordeals to Officers.

They told me if I didn't marry him, they would kill me. My father said it was for the family's honour. I had no choice but to run (23-year-old woman from Afghanistan-UNCHR)

The militia came into our village, and I was raped. After that, I knew I could not stay. I would never be safe there again. (Woman from Democratic Republic of Congo-Amnesty International)

Please click [here](#) to read a report entitled *Death in the Desert* and see a visualisation of the journeys that Africans have taken before reaching Europe and those who have never reached it.

Source: BBC

Sexual Orientation

As of 2025, homosexuality is criminalised in one-third of all countries around the World. Most of these countries are located in Africa, Asia and the Middle East. In twelve of these countries, homosexuality can also be punishable by death (Bandera, 2024). As a consequence, people who are part of the LGBT+ community are sometimes forced to flee aboard and seek asylum due to factors such as prejudice, beatings and even death threats. Although, some asylum seekers may be granted refugee status they face the additional burden of having to *prove* to the authorities that they are Gay through attending interviews that can last many hours and being compelled to fill in a detailed questionnaire that feed into stereotypical perceptions about their ‘lifestyle habits’.

They wanted proof that I'd been to a lesbian club! Not everybody can afford to go to a club

When I was a kid, my cousin and I were playing and we pretended to get married with me as the bride. When my father saw me he was so mad that he took a knife, heated it over the stove and burned a mark into my forearm (Ali)

In summary, war, famine, endemic poverty, domestic violence against women, a lack of respect for religious minorities plus a person’s sexual orientation are the leading causes why millions of human beings are being displaced at home or forced abroad to seek asylum. The age, gender and citizenship of first-time applicants to the EU are captured in figures six and seven overleaf.

Figure 6 First-time asylum applications by age and sex, March 2025 (number of applicants)

Spain: provisional data used for March 2025.
Source: Eurostat - [migr_asyappctzm](#)

Figure 7 Top 15 citizenships of first-time asylum applicants in the EU, January 24-March 2025 (number of applicants)

The ranking of top 15 citizenships is based on the aggregate for period from January 2024 to March 2025.
Spain: provisional data used for March 2025.
Source: Eurostat - [migr_asyappctzm](#)

Questionnaire feedback ^{xx}

The findings and responses from the six individuals what formed part of my primary research process, echo to a large extent what was previously outlined under the *'Lived Experiences of Asylum Seekers'*. All comments are included in Appendix D and are anonymised. In relation to *barriers* that asylum seekers encounter once they have reached Europe, respondents pointed to procedural and legal barriers, long waiting periods, a lack of information and legal aid, poor interpretation standards that may lead to misunderstandings during interviews, poor housing and lack of access to healthcare facilities plus that many have experienced trauma before and after arriving in Europe. Tragically, they increasingly experience officials who are less sympathetic than they once more (in terms of assessing applications) and that, along with increased border controls, explains in part the reduced percentage of people being granted asylum.

As far as I am aware, people fleeing persecution to reach Europe often undertake extremely dangerous and complex journeys. These routes vary based on their country of origin, geopolitical factors, and border control policies. These are mostly overland and sea routes, however, a small number also attempt to fly into Europe

People fleeing their countries take different routes, and some are even more dangerous. They go through the Mediterranean Sea to get to Europe. Others pay hefty fees to illegal agents who organize the documentation. Others come as program refugees to Europe.

Across all these routes smugglers are exploiting the difficulties people have entering Europe. Large amounts of money are being charged and people are put in grave danger. Increased controls and pushbacks at the borders of Europe are forcing migrants fleeing persecution into increasingly dangerous situations.

They face numerous barriers from unsympathetic state officials and bureaucrats who are increasingly interpreting refugee protocols and legislation in a restrictive way. This is in the context of growing international inequality, Western neo-liberal economic policies where European national-citizens are sensitised to resource allocation. Recognition rates of asylum seekers are falling and greater border controls make it even more difficult to enter into Europe. Inadequate identity documents are also used as a pretext for refusing entry.

Several **strengths** of the Pact were commented on including a revised Reception Condition Direction that provides for minimum standards of assistance to asylum applicants, promises of faster decisions, free legal counselling, minimum standards of accommodation and crucially protection for minor and families with children. Elsewhere, there was recognition of a greater

solidarity aspect within the Pact, in that it *may lead* to a greater distribution of asylum seekers across the twenty-seven Member States.

Reception Conditions Directive has been revised to provide minimum standards of assistance for asylum applicants by Member States, ensuring adequate standards of living for those arriving to the EU and seeking international protection. Ensuring free legal counselling for all applicants. The pact also seeks to ensure that decisions on asylum applications are delivered promptly

There are some positives like the protection of minors, families with children and some vulnerable immigrants

Taking away unfair burden placed on Southern European states

There was also reference to an Upskilling and Labour Market part of the Pact, which extends to a Skills and Talent Mobility Package. This foresees the creation of an EU Talent Pool via an online platform to match asylum seekers and third-country nationals with employer needs where there are shortages of labour. There is also a recommendation in the Pact to reduce the administrative barriers to the recognition of formal qualifications. In addition, collaborations called Talent Partnerships with partner countries such as Morocco and Bangladesh are foreseen, that will rollout out work placements, apprenticeships and training to align standards. Finally, new permit reforms and legal migration pathways are also included that will see a revised Single Permit Directive and a recast Blue Card Directive. It should be stressed that the later, only appears to extend to high skilled third-country nationals but not asylum seekers.

By way of contrast there were far more concerns raised about the *negative aspects* to the Pact both via by survey respondents but also when I analysed various documents written by lawyers and human right organisations. For instance, fifty NGOs sent an open letter to EU lawmakers in 2023. They assert that the Pact will be cruel and normalise the arbitrary use of detention for a range of very vulnerable categories of asylum seekers. They also argue that asylum seekers should be treated the same way as Ukrainians have been by the EU in terms of protection and assistance. A full copy of the letter is contained in Appendix H.

Major risk that the Pact results in an ill-functioning, costly, and cruel system that falls apart on implementation and leaves critical issues unaddressed.

Normalise the arbitrary use of immigration detention, including for children and families, increase racial profiling, use “crisis” procedures to enable pushbacks, and return individuals

to so called “safe third countries” where they are at risk of violence, torture, and arbitrary imprisonment.

Rather than channelling funding towards more camps, walls, and surveillance, resources should go towards providing effective solutions, based on protection and assistance, of the kind offered to people fleeing Ukraine. Europe’s solidarity and commitment to human rights cannot be defined by place of origin, race, ethnicity, or immigration status.

Other weaknesses about the Pact discussed included the lower age restrictions for biometric data processing, the fast tracking of applications that could mean some asylum seekers might have no access to legal guidance, a concern that the conditions in *detention centres/return hubs* could be worse than Direct Provision in Ireland and the *shipping of the people to third countries*. Many of these findings were triangulated by human right bodies that will be examined further on.

Detention centres emerging on borders outside of the EU, less acknowledgement of human rights, concerns with fingerprinting children, refusing 'genuine' applicants, removing benefit of doubt criteria, moving to the lowest denominator in terms of protections for applicants even more, encouraging people to make riskier journeys and so leading to increased mortality etc...

In terms of how the EU could address the *root causes of asylum*, several suggestions were made of which I have included a few quotes beneath. The comments have also informed my policy recommendations. However, in summary, reference was made to there being a need for improved developmental policies (e.g. tackling climate change and preventing the exploitation of natural resources in the developing world). In addition, the hypocritical stance of the EU was also critiqued in paying lip service to defending people’s human rights.

Better developmental policies based on global solidarity, states recognising they are living in an increasingly interdependent world, moving away from damaging neo-liberal policies and developing a stronger sense of solidarity within national economies to foster greater compassion, working through the UN to push for peace with wars - the whole peace agenda of the 60s and 70s has collapsed including in the Left.

Ensure that EU economic policies (e.g. trade or fisheries agreements) don't harm local economies.

Root causes are linked to economic opportunities/poverty; conflict, oppression and persecution; environmental factors; and social and political instability. Policies are needed to address these.

Curbing climate change and mitigating its effects is an imperative in order to slow down the proliferation of droughts and floods that cause displacement and migration.

Europe is the richest continent; it has ideologically used notion of defending progressive human rights as a means of sustaining a form of symbolic capital - an image that is contradicts in everyday practice.

Finally, the changing nature of political representation in the European Parliament and its influence on the final version of the Pact was asked, which will conveniently take us onto examine the public's perceptions about the Pact in the following section. However, in relation to the survey respondents' positions, the shift to the right in representative politics was raised, plus recurrent violations in human rights, and a fatalistic observation from a university sociologist that the European Parliament never really had progressive migration policies to begin with.

The centre right (like the EPP) also promotes a securitization agenda. We see the shift towards discussion of cooperation agreements with third countries to prevent people from reaching Europe or to take asylum seekers for processing, deportations of unsuccessful asylum seekers, etc.

While lip service is paid to respecting human rights the direction of travel as demonstrated by the pact is to entrench human rights violations with little regard for the root causes of displacement and forced migration.

I'm not in a position to answer this but the move to the right in the Parliament has certainly been expressed in a form of legislation and policy which uses the lowest common denominator as a basis for gaining 'solidarity' between states. But this is only one of degrees - the EU Parliament has rarely in practice had progressive policies even before the surge in right-wing governments though the rhetoric was often more positive.

Discourse Analysis

The framing of migrants

In my methodology chapter, I referenced a significant piece of discourse analysis conducted by Häkli et al whose findings I will discuss here in more detail. They identified that the word *asylum* is only referenced **fifty times in the Pact** compared to an *applicant* which is inserted **over six hundred times** (See table 2). Elsewhere they point out that human beings are selectively categorised in the Pact, which can in turn enable the formulation of data sets that is justified for ‘screening’ and ‘security’ reasons.

Table 2 The most frequently used terms when referring to migrants in the new pact documents

Term	Times used
Person(s)	639
Applicant(s)	531
Third country national(s)	384
Migrant(s)	196
People	69
Asylum seeker(s)	50
Refugee(s)	45
Total	1585

Source: Häkli, Kudžmaitė, Kallio

The quote underneath could be considered a form of neurological linguistic programming. Upon analysing the percentage of people granted asylum since 2018, this statement contained within the Pact is false. The average percentage of first instance decisions has increased from over the past seven years. Please see table 4. The percentages differ across Member States depending on the country of origin that someone has come from seeking asylum.

These [challenges] include an increasing proportion of applicants for international protection without genuine claims who are unlikely to receive protection in the Union with a resulting increased administrative burden and delays in granting protection for those in genuine need

of protection as well as persistent phenomenon of onward movement of migrants within the EU (European Commission, 2020h, p.10)

Table 3 The structure of frame analysis of the new pact

Framing encounters with migrants		
Human classification	Spatial coordination	Temporal control
Regulating who will be encountered: identifying, naming, sorting, ranking, registering	Regulating where encounters occur: concentrating, directing, containing, transferring outsourcing	Regulating the timing of encounters: ordering, sequencing, prolonging, speed, rhythm

Source: Häkli, Kudžmaitė, Kallio

Table 4 First instance decisions

Year	Percentage-First instance decisions
2024	51.4%
2023	53%
2020	41%
2019	39%
2018	41%

Source: European Union Agency for Asylum

In addition, Hakli et al demonstrate that that migrants are painted as active agents within the Pact. This can have negative consequences not just for themselves but also for other migrants and the EU, so in a sense “the New Pact is not primarily about migrants-it is about the EU” (Hakli et al, *ibid*). Previous research has referred to this as the ‘externalization of humanitarian responsibility’ (Digidiki & Bhanha, 2020, p.292). The setting of targets is not new by all accounts but linking asylum decisions with ‘fair procedures for all applicants’ could be seen to introduce a false analogy and thereby corrosive.

In the interest of swift and fair procedures for all applicants, whilst also ensuring that they stay of applicants to not qualify for international protection in the Union is not unduly prolonged...Member Status should accelerate the examination of applications of applications who are nationals...of a third country for which the share of decisions granting international protection is lower than 20% of the total number of decisions for that third country. (European Commission, 2020a, p.6-20)

Spatial notions

Spatial notions are responsible for upwards of forty percent of the Pact and one of the critical features of it are to improve the coordination of systems that are in place so that existing loopholes are closed (Hakli et al, p7). The terminology of ‘detention facilities’, ‘reception centres’ are used only once in the entire Pact, which is remarkable because this is where most asylum seekers will spend the majority of their time while their application in the future is processed in non-European countries under the new procedures. The Reception Conditions Directive will also prevent asylum seekers travelling between Member States. The justification for this is that it will enable the ‘fair treatment of migrants’.

Persons subject to this [border] procedure are not authorised to enter the Member State’s territory and should be kept at the external borders, or in their proximity, or in transit zones, where Member States are unable to keep them in those locations, they can use other locations within their territory (European Commission, 2020a, p.15)

In summary, I would contend that the ‘framing of human beings’ in the Pact discourse is critical to how an Immigration Officer might access a person’s application for asylum/refugee status and/or how they might be treated on arrival at a detention centre. Some of the language used within the Pact is cold in nature and inappropriate in the circumstances of genuine person fleeing *persecution*. I will now examine this key component and other aspects such as fingerprints for Eurodac and the monitoring of fundamental rights during screening and the asylum board procedure. These will be referenced by insights from the following organisations.:

- European Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA);
- Irish Human Rights and Equality Council;
- Commissioner for Human Rights of Council of Europe.

In doing so, this will provide an objective oversight analysis of whether the Pact is *in accordance with international human rights* as outlined in my research Aim. I will discuss whether the Pact is in keeping with the values of *social justice* in my conclusions section.

European Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA).

The European Agency for Fundamental Rights was established back in 2007 to oversee freedoms and values outlined in the EU Charter for Fundamental Rights. In the run up to the signing of the Pact, the FRA issued papers about:

- Planned return hubs in third countries;
- Obligations of individuals to provide fingerprints for Eurodac;
- Guide to independent national mechanisms in relation to asylum border procedures.

In relation to return-hubs, the FRA point out that they are not a “rights-free zone” and that their creation would “*only be compatible with EU law if accompanied by a clear and robust set of safeguards...Article 4 and 19 of the Charter prohibit any transfer if third-country nationals moved there would be exposed to serious harm, to inhuman or degrading treatment...and that third-country nationals who reach Member States territory ..must be channelled into national asylum procedures in full compliance with the European Convention on Human Rights and the 1951 Geneva Convention relating to the Status of Refugees*” (FRA, 2025, p.4).

The FRA conclude that irregular migrants have a *duty* to provide fingerprints for Eurodac but a refusal to do so does *not* enable Member States to ignore the notion of *non-refoulement*. Only in exceptional circumstances can a country deprive someone of their liberty and pressurise them into providing a fingerprint and that it is not conceivable that the use of force to obtain a fingerprint could be justified. The use of force “may in certain circumstances meet the threshold of inhuman treatment...prohibited by Article 4 of the Charter and Article 3 of the European Court of Human Rights” (ibid, p.8).

Elsewhere, Member States are required to establish *independent national mechanisms* in relation to asylum border procedures under Article 43(4)/Regulation EU 2024/1356 of the Asylum Procedure Regulation/ Regulation EU 2024/1348. The safeguards to guarantee this should involve the Ombudsman, NGOs and human rights institutions. A sequence of building blocks to help roll this out are outlined in some detail that include matters such as facilitating investigations, staffing and expertise to name but a few. There is also a section covering the use of Return Directives opt-out clause in *external* border cases, but which cannot be applied at *internal* borders.

Irish Human Rights and Equality Commission

As recently as July 2025, the Irish Human Rights and Equality Commission released a press release about the General Scheme of the International Protection Bill 2025, which extended to:

- Legislative Process and Timelines;
- State Capacity and Implementation Readiness;
- Vulnerability Assessments;
- Digital processing of applications;
- Detention and *De Facto* Detention;
- Legal Representation;
- Legal counselling;
- Age-Disputed Minors;
- Victims of Human Trafficking.

In summary, the IHREC argued that the bill needed to be properly examined by the Oireachtas, or it could be challenged in the courts. Doubts were raised about whether the quality of services mentioned in the Pact could be delivered by June 2026 given the previous failures under the International Protection Act 2015 and the digital literacy of some asylum seekers in the context of the self-processing their own applications and the ongoing failure to provide accommodation were raised. The power to arrest and detain adults and children without warrant (akin to internment in Northern Ireland in the 1970s), along with biometric and electronic surveillance, plus the fact that Ireland is the only EU Member States not to have ratified the Optional Protocol on the Convention Against Torture are matters of serious concern for the IHREC.

The IHREC also state the *limitations on access to legal advice and representation* under Article 47 of the EU's Charter of Fundamental Rights will be challenged in the courts and that the State should undertake legal counselling throughout the International Protection process as is set out in the Pact *instead* of expecting solicitors to under existing rules. In the context of age-disputed minors, the Commission has concerns about children being fast tracked into a 12-week asylum seekers procedure because of a lack of clarity on how age assessments will be conducted and that Ireland should align with obligations for EU Anti-Trafficking victims of human trafficking some of whom won't have documentation. Emily Cunliffe, from the School of Law in Trinity College highlighted a key criticism about the Asylum Procedures Regulation due to challenges in meeting deadlines within the EU at present and the concept of the legal fiction of non-entry whereas in relation to the Asylum and Migration Management Regulation

key criticisms extend to the punitive nature of it and question marks about whether the new system would improve when the existing one is not.

This is a once-in-a-generation overhaul of our asylum system. We must get it right. In our analysis of the current draft proposals, the Commission believes the State is in danger of introducing a system that fails to respect and vindicate the fundamental rights of international protection applicants. The proposals regarding detention of asylum seekers, access to legal representation and counselling, and the treatment of children and vulnerable persons give rise to particular concerns (Liam Herrick, Chief Commissioner)

Commissioner for Human Rights of Council of Europe

The Council of the Europe's Commissioner for Human Rights, Michael O'Flaherty, has chastised many EU Member States throughout 2025 for potential and actual breaches of human rights. In May, he reprimanded nine EU Member States (Italy, Denmark, Austria, Belgium, the Czech Republic, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and Poland) who between them signed on open letter asking for a rethink about the convention on human rights (Euronews, 2025). The Commissioner questioned the lack of reference to Article 1 Universal Declaration of Human Rights (Appendix C), whereby:

All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights" while recognising the low trust in politics at present, misinformation, and inequalities that exist while pointing out that this is not to time to pick apart human right laws that took years to negotiate after the Second World War (Commissioner for Human Rights, Michael O'Flaherty)

In July, he came out forcibly against a Greek proposal to suspend the registration of applications of people from North Africa who arrive by boat and urged the parliament to reject it. He stated that:

This proposal would legalise returning people to face a risk of torture and other serious violations, in breach of obligations under the European Convention on Human Rights, the 1951 Refugee Convention, as well as other instruments, such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. I am also aware of additional measures announced in parliament by Prime Minister Mitsotakis yesterday,

including the arrest and detention of all those concerned by this amendment which, if implemented, would raise further issues of compliance with international human rights law

We can clearly see therefore that some Member States are simply prepared to ignore international law even *before* the EU Asylum and Migration Pact has even come into force.

Data protection breaches and pushbacks

Frontex an EU agency were found to have deliberately shared information about *13,000 people and human right activists* to the European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation (El Pais, 2025). Although Frontex were forced to change their protocols by another EU agency (European Data Protection Supervisor), the damage has already been done, and it is not possible to fully ascertain how the information shared with Europol has impacted on these people's lives.

Source: Graffiti in La Ferté-sous-Jouarre (Seine-et-Marne, France)

However, it is even more perturbing that [Frontex](#) has also been involved in *illegal pushbacks* at European borders to such an extent that it has become normalised. It is therefore perhaps not surprising that that of the €81 billion earmarked to be spent by the EU from 2028-2034 on migration, asylum, border management and internal security, €11.9 billion will be allocated to Frontex alone (PICUM, 2025b). Unfortunately, human rights activists who help undocumented migrants are increasingly being criminalised for doing so, a factor that is rarely reported on by the media. 64 per cent of the help provided to asylum seekers were those who

were ‘at sea’ and the remainder on land (The Civil Fleet, 2024). For more information, please click on the following [Podcast](#) Episode 74: Is solidarity a crime.

My whole life was in that police file: my relatives, my calls to my mother, even false details about my sexual life. They wanted to portray me as promiscuous, a lesbian, using morality to make me look suspicious (Helena Maleno, human rights defender)

The normalisation of pushbacks has become so pervasive that discussing it almost feels commonplace and is deeply concerning. It reflects a shift in how European borders are managed and raises serious questions about the erosion of longstanding principles of refugee protection

Public’s perceptions of irregular migration

I discovered that there is generally very little genuine public knowledge about the minutiae of the Pact. Instead that was only a general sentiment about it, and this was generally located within a much broader narrative about the *positive and negative effects of irregular migration*. I have placed social media comments from the Irish public about migration into **Appendix F** sourced from online newspaper The Journal. The two quotes in the footnotes provide opposite viewpoints.^{xxi}

European Elections

It was possible to ascertain a barometer about the public’s views around irregular migration elsewhere. IPSOS, a consultancy firm surveyed 26,000 respondents across 18 member states in the run up to the 2024 European elections. The survey established that 51 percent had ‘negative perception’ of the EU’s impact on migration policy while only 16 percent held a ‘positive impression. 32 percent thought that the impact of the policy has been ‘neither been positive or negative’. This trend cut across gender, age and occupation (Euronews, online, 2024) and even one’s political allegiances from either people who vote for right- or left-wing parties.^{xxii} Please see figures 8 and 9. By way of contrast, the longitudinal European Social Survey from 2002 to 2018, suggests that across most European countries, people have become “more supportive of tolerant immigration policies, although outright open-border policies have minimal support...with only about 25 percent of respondents against migration, feeling that migration threatens their country’s way of life, culture and economy” (Mixed Migration Centre, 2024, pp. 245-250).

In summary, the fact that over half of all those polled by IPSOS held negative views about irregular migration would suggest that they have not been convinced by 'humanist values' and see the need to strengthen border controls either oblivious to some of the consequences of this or in full knowledge about what is happening at present. However, the European Social Survey findings differ significantly to that of IPSOS.^{xxiii} The use of Artificial Intelligence to create fake news adverts that can be shared with to a vast audience in a matter of minutes has become more prevalent in recent years. Please see footnote for information about AI and geo-political changes.^{xxiv}

Figure 8 How important is the fight against irregular migration by country?

Source: Ipsos for Euronews (March 2024)

Figure 9 How important is the fight against irregular migration by voting intention?

Source: Ipsos for Euronews (March 2024)

Chapter 6: Recommendations

My twenty policy recommendations are explored through the themes of a *political, economic, social, environmental, and cultural* framework of analysis. Some recommendations could fit under different sub-headings. The European Commission's *Directorate-Generale for Migration* must interact with other DGs in the Commission along with the other world institutions that constitute the EU in more imaginative ways.^{xxv} What appears certain, is that the EU is determined to intentionally reduce the percentage of persons who obtain refugee status under the *Pact*. This is in contravention of Article 2 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

Political

1. The capacity of EU Members States and their readiness to implement aspects of the Pact is questionable. Countries must recruit significant numbers of Immigration Officers to process backlogs in asylum cases even before the Pact becomes operational (See Appendix I for a breakdown per country). This will ensure that they follow the correct steps for someone [applying for asylum](#) and are not expedited for political reasons.^{xxvi} Despite some of the identified advantages of the Pact, a faster asylum process does not necessarily mean a fairer one.^{xxvii}

2. The return of people whose asylum applications are rejected must be carried out respectfully and in line with standards set down.^{xxviii}

3. In relation to the digital processing of asylum cases under the Pact, exemptions should be granted to individuals who are illiterate and minors. Greater accommodation as to their needs should be afforded. This would extend in particular to people who fall under vulnerability assessments. The toolkit and [video](#) developed by the European Union Agency for Asylum are especially important in this context.

4. The European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights submitted nine principles to the Council of Europe's Steering Committee for child rights around age assessments and guardianship for unaccompanied children. This aspect of the Pact must be applied correctly or

otherwise there is a grave danger that children will be identified as adults and fast tracked under the twelve-week asylum border procedure.^{xxix}

5.The practice of arbitrarily arresting people in countries as exposed by Lighthouse Reports and keeping them in detention centres must end immediately. This is in contravention of Article 9 of Universal Declaration of Human Rights.^{xxx}

6.The limitations to access legal representation under the Pact at key points of the administrative process appear to contravene Article 47 of the EU Convention of Human Rights. The EU must revisit this aspect of the Pact as it will inevitably be challenged in the Courts.

7.Ireland should sign the Optional Protocol on the Convention Against Torture before the Pact becomes operational being the only EU Member State not to have done so.

8.The responsibility for providing ‘legal counselling’ for people going through the International Protection process should fall on the Irish State and not barristers and solicitors.

9. The EU must continue to draft and implement new legislation in the form of the Digital Services Act to counteract lies and hatred spread on social media platforms that undermine the rule of law and decouple advertising space permitted to far-right groups.

Environmental

10. The EU should be doing more to live up to its obligations and international targets in reducing carbon and methane emissions, which in turn are impacting on the developing world and causing the displacement of millions of people. A ‘Global Methane Pledge’ to reduce methane emissions by 30 per cent between 2020 and 2030 was signed by 121 countries at COP

26. The EU must take the lead as it has an obligation under number 13 of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals under Climate Action.^{xxxix}

11. The EU should increase its budget for SD Goal 14-*Life below water* targeting regional fisheries management organisations. Overfishing occurring off the coast of Africa due to EU companies has devastating consequences for coastal communities all along the west coast of the Continent.

Social

13. Ireland must provide for the accommodation needs of *all* asylum seekers after the ruling of the European Court of Justice. 942 people were still awaiting an accommodation offer in August 2025 (CJEU, 2025). A recent Health Information and Quality Authority report identified that six International Protection Accommodation Service centres were sub-standard (McCurry, 2025)

14. Government departments and news channels^{xxxix} should convey more positive news stories to the public about how asylum seekers are upskilling themselves and are taking up employment in sectors of the economy to counteract far right lies and propaganda. Social media platforms can also be used to drive positive new stories.^{xxxix}

Cultural

15. The United Nations, African Union and the EU must step up their commitments to achieve gender equality for women as included under Number 5 of the Sustainable Development Goals.

^{xxxix}

16. The United Nations has a Special Rapporteur on religious intolerance mandated through [resolution 3/7](#). The United Nations general assembly has a moral duty to extend the time period of this post for an additional three years beyond 2025.^{xxxix}

17. The United Nations, African Union and the EU must work together collectively to tackle the ongoing abuses of minorities including LGCTIQ+ people to encourage countries to repeal

regressive legislation and to remove the death penalty against homosexuals in thirteen countries. Please refer to fact sheet EUAA/2024/27 for some useful information (EUAA, 2024d).

Diagram-Institutions of the European Union

Economic

18. The exporting of aircraft, guns and tanks by European weapon manufactures to war torn countries in North Africa and the Middle East must stop as this only prolongs wars and leads to people having to seek asylum. This would inevitably financially harm some EU countries who hold large shares in such companies, but international regulations and treaties must be enforced (Euronews, 2021).

19. The Asylum and Migration Fund post 2027 needs to be increased significantly way beyond the current allocation of €9.88 billion and the budget of Frontex has almost doubled to €11.9 billion should be reduced.

20. Extended pathways to migration must be implemented by the EU as several Member States populations are rapidly ageing. The Upskilling and Labour Market plus the Skills and Talent Mobility Package aspect within the Pact should be introduced before July 2026 as this offers an opportunity to fill labour market gaps in the economies of Member States.^{xxxvi}. See overleaf to view maps that show the projected population decline across European out to 2100 with and without migration patterns.

Visualised: Europe's population crisis

Map 5: Projected change in the population without migration 2100

Source: Guardian graphic

Map 6: Projected change in the population with migration 2100

Source: Guardian graphic

Figure 10: Population projects across Europe 2100

Europe faces large population declines without immigration

Population projections across Europe, scenario **with migration** versus scenario **without migration**

Guardian graphic. Source: Eurostat population projections, UK Office for National Statistics. Scenario with migration is based on a country's average net migration levels from up to 20 years ago, depending on data availability. Scenario without excludes this input in the projection model and is based on natural population dynamics.

Chapter 6: Conclusions

The dissertation set out to examine whether the *Pact* is in accordance with international human rights and the values of social justice. In some ways, I believe the research problem has been superseded by the *realpolitik* occurring at present. The findings and analysis section disclosed breaches of international law being perpetrated by EU agencies and some Member States even *before* the *Pact* has become operational. Their actions show a disdain for the Charter of Fundamental Rights and exposes the doublespeak of what is now essentially an economic bloc, irrespective of its much-heralded European Pillar of Social Rights, which contains no reference to asylum or refugees (EPR, 2017). It has been claimed that the *Pact* has “attracted sustained and serious criticism for being unbalanced, fraught with contingencies, deviating from the goal of harmonisation, and in some respects, downright unlawful” (Smyth, 2024, p.23). As such, the *Pact* appears to be principally driven by the fear of larger-scale migration occurring in the future.^{xxxvii} The contrast in how the EU has extended temporary protection status to Ukrainian refugees compared to its treatment of African, Asian and South American asylum seekers is galling.

At world-record speed, the EU put in place generous provisions to ensure that Ukrainians were given full access to housing, education, health and employment, but no similar provisions have been made for smaller numbers of people moving from Africa or Asia. In fact, the EU seems to be going everything it can to deter them (Andrew Geddes, Professor of Migration Studies)

The *turn* to the right in Western politics that first started in the United States of America has mutated like a virus across the Atlantic Ocean only to permeate the migration policies of even social-democratic parties such as in Denmark. The far-right has cannibalised centre-right parties in some EU Member States and more worryingly their communication methods have influenced the EU institutions and shaped public policy. Unfortunately, the far-right have become the primary *disruptors* of the twenty-first century emboldened through platforms such as FACEBOOK and X, but more recently Artificial Intelligence to create a more nuanced version of *Newspeak* than seems to infiltrate and alter the *reality* of a portion of society to a greater extent than possibly envisaged by George Orwell in 1984. Please click [here](#) and listen to an interview with a whistle-blower who worked for Cambridge Analytica to learn how the [reality] of the USA was changed. One of the key takeaways is that *culture* drives politics. The

last sentence from the quote in my *endnote*^{xxxviii} is chilling and reminiscent of the radical ideology of the Khmer Rouge regime in 1970s Cambodia.

Tragically, there is now a distinct likelihood that the EU will *further breach peoples human rights in the future* but only in a more draconian way under the Pact's [new outsourcing plans](#). The Commission has recently proposed changes to the concept of safe third countries (European Commission, 2025), which if implemented would limit the “suspensive effects of appeals against transfers” (De La Feld, online, 2025). This would result in asylum seekers living in a state of limbo and not belonging to any country. The definition of a safe third country (STC) was changed last year under the reform of asylum laws that will made is easier for a Member State to designate a country as a STC *even when it does not respect the 1951 Refugee Convention* (ECRE, 2025). Undeterred, the Commission remains committed to the idea but ultimately the European Court of Human Rights could decide on the legality of STCs.^{xxxix}

In a ray of hope, and a significant rebuke to the concept, the Court of Justice of the European Union has ruled that a “country can only be considered “safe” for repatriation if “the entire population” is protected across all regions (Politico, online, 2025). This undoubtedly represents a blow to the Albanian model that Italy has been pursuing recently with the backing of the Commission. Elsewhere, the European Court of Justice also ruled in favour of asylum seekers who had been denied accommodation (Bathke, 2025).

On the one hand, the law serves as a critical tool to hold governments and private actors accountable for human rights violations. On the other hand, it can sometimes be used to legitimise and facilitate severe forms of violence values (Itamar Mann, Associate Professor of Law at the University of Haifa)

Social Justice

I believe that one of the strengths of this dissertation is that it demonstrates why people *have* to seek asylum, albeit they are finding it ever more difficult to do so. The social theory pessimist Michel Foucault put forward several compelling reasons why human rights matter in in his lecture ‘Confronting Government: Human Rights’, which strongly resonates with me as someone who believes in Global Ethics.

There exists an international citizenship that has its own rights and its duties, and that obliges one to speak out against every abuse of power, whoever its author, whoever its victims. After all, we are all members of the community of the governed, and thereby obliged to show mutual solidarity

Because they claim to be concerned with the welfare of societies, governments arrogate to themselves the right to pass off as profit or loss the human unhappiness that their decisions provoke or their negligence permits. It is a duty of this international citizenship to always bring the testimony of people's suffering to the eyes and ears of governments, suffering for which it's untrue that they are not responsible. The suffering of men must never be a silent residue of policy. It grounds an absolute right to stand up and speak to those who hold power (Foucault, 1994, p.474-475)

These two powerful statements indicate that concepts such as decency, duty, ethics, welfare and cosmopolitanism are core to achieving social justice for asylum seekers/climate refugees. Many asylum seekers now live with a sense of futility much like the first is *Solitude*, which is partly influenced by the story of Jeremiah in the Old Testament and his feeling of futility in the face of injustice but also the rise of fascism in the 1930s that led to crimes of humanity against Jewish and gypsy people. In many ways, it appears as though we are revisiting that extraordinary dark period in human history. The International Declaration of Human Rights and the 1951 Geneva Convention that have stood the test of time for over seventy years are increasingly coming under attack from so called liberal-western countries and politicians. The question arises as to where does this leave us all?

Source: Libbey: Image of Michael Foucault

A new enlightenment

In my literature review chapter, I indicated that I agreed with the view that ‘justice involves cultivating virtue and reasoning about the common good’ (Sandel, *ibid*). Heidegger once claimed that “we do not have any clear, common and simple relation to reality and to ourselves...that is the big problem of the Western world” ([Archivo Geopolitico](#), 1963). This statement was made decades before the advent of Smartphones. Despite advances in technology, we have increasingly become even more *disconnected* from one another. Julia Kristeva another leading intellectual has called for a new form of humanism that is “capable of recognizing its source in Christian humanism” (Clogher, 2003b). Although she did so in the context of an economic downturn, the same sentiments could apply today in the context of *mass migration*. The changes occurring to the planet’s climate system will result in more people seeking refuge. *Abrupt changes* to climatic systems might open the collective consciousness of the world’s richest nations to the sufferings of their fellow human beings, if only through their own self-interest and survival.

Source: Chagalle

In my theory chapter, I suggested that artists could be seen as prophetic voices. The late Bruggeman held that only art “*is the universe of discourse in which energy is possible...and subversive art gives voice to the voiceless, exalts and includes the marginalized, and contradicts oppression through its language*” (Reyes, *ibid*). Therefore, I would like to help raise your spirits by inviting you to listen to the composition “[I WISH I KNEW HOW IT WOULD FEEL TO BE FREE](#)” written by jazz pianist Billy Taylor and Dick Dallas, but later popularised by Nina Simone. It offers us all a message of hope and inspiration.

Finally, perhaps we should seek wisdom from an old book called the *Holy Bible* and materials included from a Pastoral Letter entitled a ‘Hundred Thousand Welcomes’. They convey to us that the core belief of Christianity is that all human life is sacred and that we are made in the image of God (Genesis 1:27) and that we should love our neighbours as ourselves (Leviticus 19:18, Mark 12:31). We are also reminded of another parable of the Good Samaritan that we should love and respect others, *irrespective* of their ethnicity and religious background (Luke 10:29-37). Before he sadly passed away, the late Pope Francis articulated that in the West that:

Once more, we encounter the temptation to build a culture of walls, to raise walls, walls in our heart, walls on our land, in order to prevent this encounter with other cultures, with other people

More tellingly, Pope Francis reminded his flock that:

Faith is an encounter with Jesus, and we must do what Jesus does: encounter others.’ In other words, Ephphatha be opened (Mark 7:31-37).

Source: New Union Post

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Appendix A

Universal Declaration of Human Rights

Article 1

All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood.

Article 2

Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status. Furthermore, no distinction shall be made on the basis of the political, jurisdictional or international status of the country or territory to which a person belongs, whether it be independent, trust, non-self-governing or under any other limitation of sovereignty.

Article 3

Everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person.

Article 4

No one shall be held in slavery or servitude; slavery and the slave trade shall be prohibited in all their forms.

Article 5

No one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.

Article 6

Everyone has the right to recognition everywhere as a person before the law.

Article 7

All are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to equal protection of the law. All are entitled to equal protection against any discrimination in violation of this Declaration and against any incitement to such discrimination.

Article 8

Everyone has the right to an effective remedy by the competent national tribunals for acts violating the fundamental rights granted him by the constitution or by law.

Article 9

No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest, detention or exile.

Article 10

Everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his rights and obligations and of any criminal charge against him.

Article 11

1. Everyone charged with a penal offence has the right to be presumed innocent until proved guilty according to law in a public trial at which he has had all the guarantees necessary for his defence.
2. No one shall be held guilty of any penal offence on account of any act or omission which did not constitute a penal offence, under national or international law, at the time when it was committed. Nor shall a heavier penalty be imposed than the one that was applicable at the time the penal offence was committed.

Article 12

No one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to attacks upon his honour and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks.

Article 13

1. Everyone has the right to freedom of movement and residence within the borders of each state.
2. Everyone has the right to leave any country, including his own, and to return to his country.

Article 14

1. Everyone has the right to seek and to enjoy in other countries asylum from persecution.
2. This right may not be invoked in the case of prosecutions genuinely arising from non-political crimes or from acts contrary to the purposes and principles of the United Nations.

Article 15

1. Everyone has the right to a nationality.
2. No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of his nationality nor denied the right to change his nationality.

Article 16

1. Men and women of full age, without any limitation due to race, nationality or religion, have the right to marry and to found a family. They are entitled to equal rights as to marriage, during marriage and at its dissolution.
2. Marriage shall be entered into only with the free and full consent of the intending spouses.

3. The family is the natural and fundamental group unit of society and is entitled to protection by society and the State.

Article 17

1. Everyone has the right to own property alone as well as in association with others.
2. No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of his property.

Article 18

Everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion; this right includes freedom to change his religion or belief, and freedom, either alone or in community with others and in public or private, to manifest his religion or belief in teaching, practice, worship and observance.

Article 19

Everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers.

Article 20

1. Everyone has the right to freedom of peaceful assembly and association.
2. No one may be compelled to belong to an association.

Article 21

1. Everyone has the right to take part in the government of his country, directly or through freely chosen representatives.
2. Everyone has the right of equal access to public service in his country.
3. The will of the people shall be the basis of the authority of government; this will shall be expressed in periodic and genuine elections which shall be by universal and equal suffrage and shall be held by secret vote or by equivalent free voting procedures.

Article 22

Everyone, as a member of society, has the right to social security and is entitled to realization, through national effort and international co-operation and in accordance with the organization and resources of each State, of the economic, social and cultural rights indispensable for his dignity and the free development of his personality.

Article 23

1. Everyone has the right to work, to free choice of employment, to just and favourable conditions of work and to protection against unemployment.
2. Everyone, without any discrimination, has the right to equal pay for equal work.
3. Everyone who works has the right to just and favourable remuneration ensuring for himself and his family an existence worthy of human dignity, and supplemented, if necessary, by other means of social protection.

4. Everyone has the right to form and to join trade unions for the protection of his interests.

Article 24

Everyone has the right to rest and leisure, including reasonable limitation of working hours and periodic holidays with pay.

Article 25

1. Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond his control.
2. Motherhood and childhood are entitled to special care and assistance. All children, whether born in or out of wedlock, shall enjoy the same social protection.

Article 26

1. Everyone has the right to education. Education shall be free, at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. Elementary education shall be compulsory. Technical and professional education shall be made generally available and higher education shall be equally accessible to all on the basis of merit.
2. Education shall be directed to the full development of the human personality and to the strengthening of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. It shall promote understanding, tolerance and friendship among all nations, racial or religious groups, and shall further the activities of the United Nations for the maintenance of peace.
3. Parents have a prior right to choose the kind of education that shall be given to their children.

Article 27

1. Everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits.
2. Everyone has the right to the protection of the moral and material interests resulting from any scientific, literary or artistic production of which he is the author.

Article 28

Everyone is entitled to a social and international order in which the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration can be fully realized.

Article 29

1. Everyone has duties to the community in which alone the free and full development of his personality is possible.

2. In the exercise of his rights and freedoms, everyone shall be subject only to such limitations as are determined by law solely for the purpose of securing due recognition and respect for the rights and freedoms of others and of meeting the just requirements of morality, public order and the general welfare in a democratic society.
3. These rights and freedoms may in no case be exercised contrary to the purposes and principles of the United Nations.

Article 30

Nothing in this Declaration may be interpreted as implying for any State, group or person any right to engage in any activity or to perform any act aimed at the destruction of any of the rights and freedoms set forth herein.

Appendix B

Building blocks of the EU Asylum and Migration Pact

1. Secure external borders

Robust screening: People who do not fulfil the conditions to enter the EU will be registered, subject to identification, security, and have to undertake health checks.

Eurodac asylum and migration database: The Eurodac Regulation will see the establishment of a new asylum and migration database, ensuring clear identification of everyone who enters the EU as an asylum seeker or an irregular migrant.

Border procedure and returns: A mandatory border procedure will apply for asylum applicants who are unlikely to need protection, mislead the authorities or present a security risk. Efficient returns with reintegration support will apply for those not eligible for international protection.

Crisis protocols and action against instrumentalisation: The Crisis Regulation provides quick crisis protocols, with operational support and funding, in emergency situations.

2. Fast and efficient procedures

Clear asylum rules: The *Asylum Migration Management Regulation* will ensure a more rapid decision about which EU country is responsible for handling an application for asylum.

Guaranteeing people's rights: The *Reception Conditions Directive* will establish harmonised standards, ensure satisfactory living conditions for asylum seekers, while strengthening safeguards and improving integration processes.

EU standards for refugee status qualifications: The *Qualification Regulation* will harmonise criteria for international protection and clarifies the rights and obligations of beneficiaries.

Preventing abuses: The *Asylum Procedure Regulation* sets out clear obligations of cooperation for asylum seekers, providing for consequences in case of non-compliance.

3. Effective system of solidarity and responsibility

Permanent solidarity framework: This framework ensures that Member States will receive the solidarity needed. EU countries will be able to choose how they will participate, between relocations, financial contributions, operational support, request deductions, and '*responsibility offsets*'.

Operational and financial support: EU Agencies and EU funds will support EU countries every step of the way.

Clearer rules on responsibility for asylum applications: The new rules enhance the responsibility criteria determining the EU country responsible for assessing an asylum application.

Preventing secondary movements: Asylum seekers will have to apply for international protection in the first EU country they enter and remain there until their application is determined by the country.

4. Embedding migration in international partnerships

Preventing irregular departures: The Pact will see strengthened capacities of border management authorities with *partner countries* through reinforced cooperation with Frontex.

Fighting migrant smuggling: The Pact will see the establishment of Anti-Smuggling Partnerships with partner countries and UN agencies, tackling smuggling in specific locations.

Cooperation on readmission: The development of legal migration will strengthen cooperation on return and readmission matters.

Promoting legal pathways: An EU Talent Pool **will** establish an EU-wide platform to facilitate international recruitment, while Talent Partnerships will also allow non-EU citizens to work, study, and train in the EU.

Timeline

Source: European Commission

A common EU system to manage migration

Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2024 © European Union, 2024

<p>Secure external borders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Robust screening ▪ Eurodac asylum and migration database ▪ Border procedure and returns ▪ Crisis protocols and action against instrumentalisation 	<p>Fast and efficient procedures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Clear asylum rules ▪ Guaranteeing people's rights ▪ EU standards for refugee status qualification ▪ Preventing abuses 	<p>Effective system of solidarity and responsibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Permanent solidarity framework ▪ Operational and financial support ▪ Clearer rules on responsibility for asylum applications ▪ Preventing secondary movements 	<p>Embedding migration in international partnerships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Preventing irregular departures ▪ Fighting migrant smuggling ▪ Cooperation on readmission ▪ Promoting legal pathways

Appendix C

Letter: Attacks on the Human Rights of migrants put all our rights at risk

Recent days have witnessed horrific scenes in the small town of Ballymena in Northern Ireland. There, night after night, rioting thugs have tyrannised men, women and children simply because they come from somewhere else. The shocking scenes remind me of the recent repeated arson attacks on migration accommodation centres across the Republic of Ireland. Both phenomena have been fed at least in part by hateful online disinformation.

These scenes are played out, in one form or another, in many places across Europe. They are the unacceptable but not surprising outcome of years of the disparagement of migrants; their ‘othering’. This laying of the blame for social ills on foreigners was long the preserve of an unelectable extreme form of populist politics. However, over time, including with some changes in political fortunes, the othering of migrants has entered the mainstream.

As evidence, I would, until recently point to some media sources as well as to just a few states, particularly regarding the policing of their borders.

But recent weeks saw a worrying turn when nine countries^[1] (all of them European Union and Council of Europe member states), on 22 May, published a kind of open letter or statement on the topic of irregular migration. It is carefully phrased, but nevertheless, it weaves a narrative of a loss of control of our borders and puts a focus on the criminality of some migrants.

Turning to human rights, it argues that the balance has gone wrong – that “safety and security for the victims and the vast majority of law-abiding citizens is a crucial and decisive right. And, as a general rule, it should take precedence over other considerations”. By “other considerations” the statement presumably refers to, as it puts it, “the protection of the wrong people”.

And it is not just referring to criminals, as is evident from the reference to the need to counter hostile states that are, “for example, (..) instrumentalising migrants at our borders”.

Having laid out what it sees as the problem, the statement prescribes what is now needed, including, centrally, “a look at how the European Court of Human Rights has developed its interpretation of the European Convention on Human Rights”, since the Court, “has, in some cases, limited our ability to make political decisions in our democracies. And thereby affected how we as leaders can protect our democratic societies and our populations against the challenges facing us in the world today”. More generally, the statement observes that, “it is necessary to start a discussion about how the international conventions match the challenges that we face today. What was once right might not be the answer of tomorrow”.

There is so much to repudiate and challenge in the statement of the nine countries. It grossly over speaks the incidence of criminality within migrant communities; it refers not so much as

once to refugees fleeing persecution. It posits evidence free claims such as that the European Court of Human Rights makes the protection of our societies more difficult. It disregards how states can pursue legitimate goals like securing our borders without backtracking on respect for human rights.

What is more, it proposes the establishment of a sort of hierarchy of rights- holders, with law abiding citizens in a superior position to “the wrong people”.

And all of this is framed in a discourse suggesting that it draws its authority from the will of the people.

Where, I ask, is acknowledgement of article 1 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, whereby, “all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights”? Where is the recognition that the perceived will of the people must always be subject to the rule of law, including the application of the international human rights treaties? Where is the appreciation of the steadfast practice, in Europe at least, for human rights treaty development to always be in the service of strengthened rather than weakened protection of human beings?

As for the will of the people, I do acknowledge that this is a tricky time to govern, with waves of disinformation sweeping across our societies, patterns of deep economic inequality and low levels of trust in political and other institutions. But the answer is not to disavow our values. It is certainly not to pick at the web of human rights protections so laboriously put in place after the horrors of the Second World War.

Instead, governance should be evidence-based, addressing the true root causes of unease. It should also adopt an historical perspective, not only learning from our past but also recognising how an act of today can have appalling future consequences.

It is time to wise-up to how dangerous a moment this is. Today the focus is on migrants; tomorrow it will be another vulnerable minority group; eventually it could be any of us.

I call on the nine governments to reconsider their position. I call on all Council of Europe member states to be steadfast in protecting the human rights of everyone.

Michael O'Flaherty

Appendix D

Asylum seeker quotes

Poverty and War

The boat guys have called me - they said I should get ready. I am asking you to pray for me - the time has come (Mouhamed Oulay)

Nobody knows what could happen to me in these waters. The evil spirits of the sea could kill me

The boat could capsize, killing everyone. If you fall into the water, what would you hold on to? The only possibility is death, but you have to take risks

The motor was heating up and the wind was so strong, some of the fishermen suggested we head to Morocco. But the captain refused. He said if we moved slowly, we'd be in Spain by 6am

Everyone started arguing and insulting each other. The captain gave in and turned back to Senegal

There are a lot of us, we've filled the house. There are people from Mali and Guinea too. They take us in small boats of 10 to 15 people until we get to the big boat, then we leave

You will see people in the water who have died, but the boats keep going

There are a lot of us, we've filled the house. There are people from Mali and Guinea too. They take us in small boats of 10 to 15 people until we get to the big boat, then we leave

I did any job you can imagine, but things didn't get any better. If you don't have money, you don't matter. I am their only hope and I don't have money

I wish to go back and try again. Yes, honest to God, that is my belief. That is better for me. If I die, it is God's choice

If you take a big boat, one that can carry 200 to 300 people, and each of them pay around \$500, we are talking about a lot of money (Senegalese man-Mouhamed Oulay)

The mafias that organise trips have realised that this is like drug trafficking, with little chance of being detected (Lieutenant Antonio Fuentes, Spain's Guardia Civil set up to tackle the smugglers)

Every 45 minutes, a migrant dies trying to reach our beaches. This means trafficking mafias are increasingly becoming more powerful (Mr Clavijo, referencing data Spanish rights group Walking Borders)

For them, a migrant is a mere commodity. They carry people like they could carry drugs or weapons. They are simply victims (Police)

Minors and Religious Persecution

The day I decided to convert from Islam to Christianity, I lost everything that had been essential in my life up to that point. I lost the faith I grew up with. I lost my country and my community, where many people now wish me dead. But the most difficult to accept is that I lost my family. When my mother said, "I wish you died before telling me because for me you just died today," I felt my heart being crushed a thousand times. It was at this point that my mental health began to suffer. I left my country in July 2017 to save my own life. That was when I stopped feeling.

*I arrived in the UK when I was 23. I had nothing – no friends, no family, no home. Thankfully, I found the church, who took me in as one of their own. Now, when someone uses the term 'family', I think about my church family. For a while, I felt like life was improving. But then my asylum claim was refused by the Home Office and I was detained. I spent almost two months in detention. Alone in my cell, I stayed awake at night and slept during the day. I was depressed, undead. In detention, my flashbacks and nightmares grew worse. Eventually, I was released from detention, but the psychological damage was already done. It was at this stage that I attempted to take my own life (**Moroccan man-Mouhamed**)*

*They tried to put us in the military [in Eritria] but we escaped. But the ones who didn't escape, they are still in the military. Almost everybody escaped, even the kids escape because they know their brothers' future, what will happen in the future. That's why they try to escape when they are kids (**Unnamed, extract: My Fourth Time We Drowned, Journalist, Sally Hayden**)*

Undocumented and missing asylum seekers

*I left my country in 2009, driven by political tensions. I undertook a journey to Belgium, hoping to find a better life and protection. Once I arrived here, I realised that life without papers is extremely difficult. I don't have legal status, which means I have to work in precarious jobs, often poorly paid. I do cleaning and construction work, but I'm often exploited and have no rights. Finding stable housing is a real challenge; I often live in shared flats, sometimes in unsanitary conditions. And now I'm looking for a squat because I can no longer pay. I've tried to regularise my situation by submitting several applications, but they were all rejected. This leaves me in a constant state of uncertainty. Psychologically, it's a heavy burden. I feel a deep sense of isolation and anxiety. I dream of finding a solution to live with dignity here and, above all, to be able to start a family in Belgium (**40-year-old man from Guinea, interviewed in Brussels**)*

I live in constant fear of being arrested at any moment, fear of being deported to a country where I am no longer safe. I have no one to confide in and I don't dare to seek official help because I fear it will make my situation worse. My only hope is that one day I can live here without having to flee or hide. (40-year-old man from Guinea Conakry, interviewed in Brussels)

“At first, I was trying to look for them but my situation made me stop. I was thinking: if I find them, then what? I don't have any money, a place to stay or anything for them. I am ashamed of myself and they will be ashamed of me too when they see my situation. I want to know where they are and if they are well, then once things are better, I can reveal myself.”

(Shinne,* a Somali man in Bristol, looking for his missing brothers)

He left with another young man of his same age, his lifetime friend; his friend has not [been found] either; they simply left. They called from a beach, they said that they would sleep there, and leave the next day. That was on a Saturday. That was the last time they called

(Noor, a Moroccan woman looking for her teenage son)

We don't know which institution is responsible to offer information related to missing migrants. I don't know where to go or whom to ask in the Government. Secondly, it is impossible to go to the country where [my son] went missing because I can't afford that. What I can do is to get news from the delala [smuggler] who facilitated his journey. Though I am very disappointed in the delaloch [smugglers], I have never thought to accuse them [of my son's disappearance] also because most of them are my relatives. Also, I am scared to go to the government office because I have heard of families who sent their children through illegal ways and who were arrested and thrown into jail. Thus, what I can do is keep praying, hoping that one day my God may herald me with good news (Mother of a missing migrant from Ethiopia)

Gender violence

They told me if I didn't marry him, they would kill me. My father said it was for the family's honor. I had no choice but to run (23-year-old woman from Afghanistan-UNCHR)

The militia came into our village, and I was raped. After that, I knew I could not stay. I would never be safe there again. (Woman from Democratic Republic of Congo-Amnesty International)
The interview process is difficult for a woman. Because I had two interviews, the two interviews I had with the Home Office were with men. I'm a victim of torture, of rape, but I have to explain it to a Home Office male officer, so it's difficult for a woman to explain all these things to a strange person ... and then they say, 'Your answer was not clear, we don't believe you.' But, sometimes, I would love to say more about what happened, but, because it's a man in front of me, it's like I'm scared to say all these things in front of a strange person, so it's difficult.

Sexual orientation

The interview process is difficult for a woman. Because I had two interviews, the two interviews I had with the Home Office were with men. I'm a victim of torture, of rape, but I have to explain it to a Home Office male officer, so it's difficult for a woman to explain all these things to a strange person ... and then they say, 'Your answer was not clear, we don't believe you.' But, sometimes, I would love to say more about what happened, but, because it's a man in front of me, it's like I'm scared to say all these things in front of a strange person, so it's difficult.

They wanted proof that I'd been to a lesbian club! Not everybody can afford to go to a club

Homosexuality in Iran is punishable by death, and many people like me escape Iran to Turkey and other countries to have their basic and fundamental human rights. It is very difficult. The Iranian LGBT situation is very crucial - we don't have human rights homosexuals, we have discrimination and violation of human rights. I hope that one day Iranian LGBTs have their own freedom and don't need to escape Iran to have the very basic that lots of people take for granted.

When I was a kid, my cousin and I were playing and we pretended to get married with me as the bride. When my father saw me he was so mad that he took a knife, heated it over the stove and burned a mark into my forearm (Ali)

Online Responses from Research Participants

1. Could you tell me about the types of journeys people fleeing persecution have to undertake to reach Europe?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Response Total
<p>As far as I am aware, people fleeing persecution to reach Europe often undertake extremely dangerous and complex journeys. These routes vary based on their country of origin, geopolitical factors, and border control policies. These are mostly overland and sea routes, however, a small number also attempt to fly into Europe.</p>		
<p>People fleeing their countries take different routes, and some are even more dangerous. They go through the Mediterranean Sea to get to Europe . Others pay hefty fees to illegal agents who organize the documentation. Others come as program refugees to Europe.</p>		
<p>Other people use their documents and flee to Europe, depending on the situation in their home country.</p>		
<p>Lots of routes to Europe: - across Mediterranean: Eastern route from Turkey to Greece; Central route from North Africa to Italy & Malta; Western route to Spain. - Western Balkans route (across land)</p>		
<p>Across all these routes smugglers are exploiting the difficulties people have entering Europe. Large amounts of money are being charged and people are put in grave danger. Increased controls and pushbacks at the borders of Europe are forcing migrants fleeing persecution into increasingly dangerous situations.</p>		
<p>This is a very vague question. It depends on the countries they are travelling from. Some can be very hazardous crossings by land and eventually by sea, in inadequate boats. The numbers of worldwide deaths have risen to almost 9,000 according to IOM figures in 2024 but these are significant underestimates of the reality Most people just disappear and have no there is no recognition of them every existing. . Responsibility often falls on 'people smugglers', 'traffickers' etc. They are only partially to blame given they provide a poor service in the context of increasing state restrictions and border controls.</p>		

2. Could you tell me about the barriers they face in claiming asylum and gaining refugee status within the EU?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Response Total
<p>An individual can face numerous legal, procedural, and practical barriers when trying to claim asylum and gain refugee status in the EU.</p> <p>Legal barriers: Dublin Regulation (Requires asylum seekers to apply for asylum in the first EU country they enter).</p> <p>Procedural Barriers: Short timeframe for lodging applications, Practical difficulties for applicants traveling to Dublin to express intent; Long waiting periods for interviews and decisions, delays, lack of legal aid and information.</p> <p>Other barriers: Inadequate or poor-quality interpretation during asylum interviews can lead to misunderstandings or inconsistent testimony; provide documentation or credible evidence; Poor housing, lack of healthcare, or unsafe accommodation</p>		
<p>Language barriers</p> <p>Legal Support</p> <p>Documentation</p> <p>Cultural Differences</p> <p>Policies</p>		
<p>First barrier is the efforts the EU is going to in order to stop people from arriving on EU soil; also forced returns and externalisation asylum and migration management through third country agreements.</p>		
<p>By the time people manage to get to Europe they are likely to have experienced trauma in their countries of origin or along their journey. This is compounded by the manner in which they are treated – poor living conditions, isolation and exclusion, discrimination and in some cases violence. Language barriers are difficult to overcome and employment is hard to come by.</p>		
<p>Complex legal and administrative systems also make it extremely difficult for people trying to get refugee status. Lack of access to legal aid makes it difficult to navigate the legal systems and to present their case.</p>		
<p>Physical and mental health difficulties are compounded by lack of access to services and supports.</p>		
<p>They face numerous barriers from unsympathetic state officials and bureaucrats who are increasingly interpreting refugee protocols and legislation in a restrictive way. This is in the context of growing international inequality, Western neo-liberal economic policies where European national-citizens are sensitised to resource allocation. Recognition rates of asylum seekers are falling and greater border</p>		

2. Could you tell me about the barriers they face in claiming asylum and gaining refugee status within the EU?

controls make it even more difficult to enter into Europe. Inadequate identity documents are also used as a pretext for refusing entry.

answered	4
skipped	2

3. Could you discuss the policy submissions your organisation or party has submitted to the Institutions of the European Union in advance of the signing off of the EU asylum and migration pact?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Response Total
<p>My organisation has not been able to send any documents but is working with local NGOs s in advocating for Asylum and putting strategies on how to support Asylum seekers</p> <hr/> <p>We haven't made any formal submissions to the EU on the Pact. However we have made a submission to the Oireachtas Justice Committee on the General Scheme of the bill to give effect to it. We're also part of the civil society Coalition that made a submission.</p>		

4. In what way has the changing nature of the political representation of the European Parliament changed the debate and final version of the EU asylum and migration pact?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Response Total
<p>Migration became highly politicised Rise of right-wing and populist parties Most of Anti- anti-migration leaders have found a platform to enforce and change migration policies by adding Stronger border enforcement measures. The Left wing is outnumbered and their voices are silenced.</p> <hr/> <p>There has been a shift to the right in European representative politics. Parties on the right and far right see migration as a threat and is quite explicit about wanting to protect the external borders while being less concerned with human rights violations at them.</p> <hr/> <p>The centre right (like the EPP) also promotes a securitization agenda. We see the shift towards discussion of cooperation agreements with third countries to prevent people from reaching Europe or to take asylum seekers for processing, deportations of unsuccessful asylum</p>		

4. In what way has the changing nature of the political representation of the European Parliament changed the debate and final version of the EU asylum and migration pact?

seekers, etc.

While lip service is paid to respecting human rights the direction of travel as demonstrated by the pact is to entrench human rights violations with little regard for the root causes of displacement and forced migration.

We see this in Ireland too – government talks about being “firm but fair” on migration and there are worrying aspects to the proposed legislation to give effect to it.

I'm not in a position to answer this but the move to the right in the Parliament has certainly been expressed in a form of legislation and policy which uses the lowest common denominator as a basis for gaining 'solidarity' between states. But this is only one of degree- the EU Parliament has rarely in practice had progressive policies even before the surge in right wing government though the rhetoric was often more positive.

5. What would you see are the potential strengths of the EU asylum and migration pact?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Response Total
<p>Reception Conditions Directive has been revised to provide minimum standards of assistance for asylum applicants by Member States, ensuring adequate standards of living for those arriving to the EU and seeking international protection. Ensuring free legal counselling for all applicants. The pact also seeks to ensure that decisions on asylum applications are delivered promptly,</p>		
<p>The EU pact, for me, I don't see any positive way as it has so many unfair measures that will affect people who are already in a vulnerable position. The Border controls and lack of legal support for people seeking asylum and detention are violating their rights.</p>		
<p>In principle the pact would allow EU countries to respond to migration and asylum based on principles of cooperation, solidarity and shared responsibility with an approach that is grounded in respect for human rights. However, it fundamentally fails to protect the human rights or dignity of asylum seekers in particular.</p>		
<p>There are some positives like the protection of minors, families with children and some vulnerable immigrants.</p>		

5. What would you see are the potential strengths of the EU asylum and migration pact?

Taking away unfair burden placed on Southern European states

6. What would you see are the potential weaknesses of the EU asylum and migration pact?

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Response Total
1	Open-Ended Question	100.00%	4
<p>Mandatory screening for security checks. There are no legal rights for asylum seekers in this process.</p> <p>There is a limit on the issuing of travel documents to asylum seekers. Border procedures detention have increased from 4 to 12 weeks however if the courts does not decide in 21 days the person must be released.</p> <p>It is easier to detain people under the reception conditions.</p> <p>Lower age restrictions for biometric data collection (Eurodac). There is a lot of data privacy regulations and GDPR concerns for the storage of people's data. The legislation states you can use corrosion on children to obtain the fingerprint and also facial recognition from children which is problematic.</p> <hr/> <p>Implementing Detention centers if we are already fighting the Direct Provision, we can already foresee that the conditions of Detention Centers will be worse.</p> <p>The fast tracking of the Applications means that people have no access to legal guidance, which violates their right to have legal guidance during the application.</p> <p>The shipping of the people to third countries</p> <p>Language barriers for some people need enough support to fill in their application and some people have varying level of literacy</p> <hr/> <p>The main issues with the pact is that, despite its name, it is intended to deal with irregular migrants who claim asylum rather than migration in general. As a case in point, the EU faces labour shortages but the pact offers nothing by way of solution to the emergent needs.</p> <hr/> <p>The pact is intended to reduce the numbers seeing asylum not to protect them. Main weaknesses are around potential violations of fundamental rights, detention of asylum seekers, and lac of adequate safeguards. The reliance on border procedures is a real concern.</p> <hr/> <p>Detention centres emerging on borders outside of the EU, less acknowledgement of human rights, concerns with fingerprinting children, refusing 'genuine' applicants, removing benefit of doubt criteria, moving to the lowest denominator in terms of protections for</p>			

6. What would you see are the potential weaknesses of the EU asylum and migration pact?

applicants even more, encouraging people to make riskier journeys and so leading to increased mortality etc...

7. How could or should the EU address the root causes that force people to flee their homeland?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Response Total
<p>Invest in diplomacy, conflict resolution, and mediation efforts in fragile states. Foster fair trade partnerships and support job creation in countries of origin. Ensure that EU economic policies (e.g. trade or fisheries agreements) don't harm local economies.</p> <p>Develop safe and legal channels (e.g., humanitarian visas, resettlement, labour migration) to reduce irregular and dangerous journeys.</p>		
<p>Root causes are linked to economic opportunities/poverty; conflict, oppression and persecution; environmental factors; and social and political instability. Policies are needed to address these.#</p>		
<p>Policies that promote economic development rather than restricting or undermining economic growth would help. So would working to prevent and resolve conflicts, not just providing humanitarian assistance to those affected by conflict. Curbing climate change and mitigating its effects is an imperative in order to slow down the proliferation of droughts and floods that cause displacement and migration.</p>		
<p>Better developmental policies based on global solidarity, states recognising they are living in an increasingly interdependent world, moving away from damaging neo-liberal policies and developing a stronger sense of solidarity within national economies to foster greater compassion, working through the UN to push for peace with wars - the whole peace agenda of the 60s and 70s has collapsed including in the Left.</p>		

8. How does that differ from your approach as an organisation or party, "if at all"?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Response Total
We don't have enough control and resources beyond our borders		
NA		

9. On reflection, do you think that the EU asylum and migration pact is in accordance with international human rights and the values of social justice?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Response Total
It is not for the reason that I have stated above. There is a violation of human rights or it is more prone to that, and we are already seeing it in other states .		
No its not.		
See analyses done by organisations like Amnesty International.		
Not necessarily, in terms of rhetoric and reality it has moved too far away from these		

10. Finally, is there anything else you would like to add or other important aspects I might have forgotten to question you about?

Answer Choices	Response Percent	Response Total
<p>Here are few concerns regarding the operationalisation and implementation of the EU Pact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Externalising applications risks international protection principles. • Shifting refugee protection to non-EU countries risks human rights. • Anti-immigrant sentiment and misinformation impacting implementation. • Protection of human rights not prioritised in the system. • The system is designed to make things more restrictive and control the flow of migration. <p>Concerns regarding the Irish immigration system in general.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Homelessness among asylum seekers. • Assessment of unaccompanied minors. • Quality of interpretation services. • Direct provision accommodation services. • Misinformation and far-right influence in politics. 		

10. Finally, is there anything else you would like to add or other important aspects I might have forgotten to question you about?

- Racism and lack of legal protection against it.
- Institutional racism in the two-tiered system (e.g. Difference in treatment of Ukrainian refugees and other asylum seekers)

I'm currently working on a piece about the international protection system in Ireland, and SJI will be publishing a paper on it soon—I'll share it with you once it's complete. SJI has also published two papers under the "Migrations in Our Common Home" series: (1) Responding with Care – Ireland's Response to the Ukrainian Crisis, and (2) Planning for Change – Climate Change and Migration. Both may be worth checking out.

None Thank you for contacting me and also would like to read the report or research an good luck

Europe is the richest continent, it has ideologically used notion of defending progressive human rights as a means of sustaining a form of symbolic capital - an image that is contradicts in everyday practice.

Appendix E

Individuals and organisations invited to participate

Allison Kinneally, Lecturer, South East Technological University
Amnesty International, Executive Director Mr Bowen
Aodhán Ó Ríordáin, Member European Parliament, Irish Labour Party
Associate Professor and Programme in the School of Law, UCD, Mr Thornton
Asylum and Citizenship Bar Association, Aoife McMahon BL, Chair of Immigration
Barry Andrews, Member European Parliament, Fianna Fail
Bríd Ní Chonail, Lecturer, Technological University Dublin
Catherine Costello, Professor, University College Dublin
David Conlon Smyth, SC
Doras, CEO,
Dr Lucy Micheal independent consultant
European Council on Exiles and Refugees
European Migration Network
European Union Agency for Asylum
Frontex
Irish Refugee Council, CEO,
Irish Centre for Human Rights, Galway University

Irish Human Right and Equality Commission, Mr Dixon (Commissioner)
Immigrant Council of Ireland (Chairperson & CEO)
International Migration Network
International Organisation Migration
International Protection Office
Irish Council of Civil Liberties-Joe O'Brien, Executive Director
Human Right and Equality Commission, Michael Flaherty (Commissioner)
Migration Policy Network- Yavcan Head of Research
Mixed Migration Centre- Aurelia Donnard (MMC West and North Africa)
Mixed Migration Organisation, Roberto Forin
Niloufar EDI Officer, University of Limerick
Platform for International Cooperation on Undocumented Migrants-Gary Mylona
Steven Loyal, Professor, School of Sociology, University College Dublin
Siphiwe Moyo
United Nations CHR Enda O'Neill
Social Justice Ireland

Appendix F

Online responses to asylum and migration issues

Gary Kearney^{2y}

Apr 17th 2024, 2:56 AM

@SV3tN8M4: *It is available online if you are that interested!*

1

Thomas Sheridan^{2y}

Apr 16th 2024, 8:24 AM

Remember the FG promise to end the Quangos?

Instead, they have become more pervasive, more powerful and don't see themselves answerable to the will of the people.

They are cosseted with ever increasing state funding.

Refund them now.

9

Gary Kearney^{2y}

Apr 17th 2024, 2:55 AM

@Thomas Sheridan: *A Quango and an NGO are totally different!*

Shane Kinsella (Kinsey)^{2y}

Apr 15th 2024, 7:46 AM

Hold on , he is complaining about ,

“People who have travelled on false documents will be put in detention while their application is being processed.”

What's the problem ?

That's exactly what should happen.

If I went to another country on a false document I'd be put in jail.

That's the problem with these NGOs , they are so out of touch with reality that they think certain laws shouldn't apply to them.

676

Carl Campbell^{2y}

Apr 15th 2024, 7:58 AM

Short version: NGO's are afraid their scant relevance will be further eroded and they'll lose their cushy jobs, big salaries and absolutely no oversight.

492

Gary Kearney^{2y}

Apr 17th 2024, 2:53 AM

@Carl Campbell: Do you know who are NGOs and the essential work they do? Obviously not by that off the wall comment!

1

AnthonyK^{2y}

Apr 15th 2024, 7:39 AM

If you can travel to a country for a holiday then that country is safe. If Ireland / EU trades with that country, then that country is safe.

441

Kevin Kerr^{2y}

Apr 15th 2024, 11:39 AM

@AnthonyK: Nonsense. Ireland trades with nearly every country in the world, including such human rights luminaries as North Korea, China & Saudi Arabia. You can freely travel to China or Saudi Arabia for your holidays, but what is safe for you is not necessarily safe for a Chinese or Saudi Arabian national seeking asylum in Ireland. I could come up with multiple more examples, but I suggest you do your own research – you might learn something

21

Robert Halvey^{2y}

Apr 15th 2024, 8:19 AM

There are some very wealthy people making a fortune off the whole migration mess at the exp

397

Mary.E.^{2y}

Apr 15th 2024, 10:26 AM

*@Robert Halvey:
True. A clampdown on developers, companies and individuals making tens of millions shoving immigrants into every hotel, apartment block, and house they can get their hands on.*

The government are lining these millionaire's bank accounts with obscene wealth with not a care in the world where the people or accommodation are put.

150

G

Gerry Kelly^{2y}

Apr 15th 2024, 8:53 AM

Non Government Organisations get billions of money from the government/ taxpayer. Is there not a wee bit of a contradiction there

225

Gary Kearney^{2y}

Apr 17th 2024, 2:54 AM

@Gerry Kelly: NGOs are subcontractors for the government and provide services that the government would otherwise have to do themselves.

1

B

Bat Boy^{2y}

Apr 15th 2024, 9:30 AM

The immigration crisis has gone far enough and NGOs are part of this. The current system provides too much time for financial refugees which takes away from citizens of the host countries and genuine refugees who get caught up in a clogged system. Identity financial refugees quickly and remove them, likewise find the genuine cases, support and integrate.

214

N

Nicholas Grubb^{7y}

Apr 15th 2024, 8:53 AM

God these NGO Bleeding Heart lot annoy me. Its always the individual sad case, not the fifty million who would come in to Europe if the door was open the way they want it to be. Good solution for the send backs. Let the UN as part of a Russia / Ukraine settlement, take over Crimea. It will never work with one of the protagonists getting it. It could become a new homeland for several million to eventually be handed over to the newcomers once up and running.

135

Thesaltyurchin^{7y}

Apr 15th 2024, 8:01 AM

Not enough poor people. need more.

120

F

Frank McGlynn ^{1y}

Apr 15th 2024, 2:46 PM

@Thesaltyurchin: to justify the creation of more NGOS to enhance the career prospects of those in the NGO golden circle.

45

Chaotic State ^{2y}

Apr 15th 2024, 4:42 PM

Yet another NGO spokesperson with a vested interest in keeping the immigration /migration gravy train rolling with a careless regard for either the migrants arriving in Ireland or the people already living here.

Their motto, and that of the current government is usually ” If there is room on the floor, then there is room for more”

Ireland needs an Asylum system that works as the current policy is having a devastating impact on all of the social services in this country, especially Housing, Health and Education.

It's not fair on the people arriving or the citizen's already living in Ireland.

Immigration needs to be controlled for Security and Health and Safety, and when our social services are overwhelmed then the government needs to act by capping the number's arriving.

For health and safety reasons there are capacity limits on every venue in the country. Croke Park has a capacity of 82,300 so you wouldn't sell 200,000 tickets for the All Ireland for obvious reasons. Our country shouldn't be treated any differently for the health, safety, and welfare of us all.

71

Keth Tgi ^{2y}

Apr 15th 2024, 12:46 PM

Again we see certain groups, the NGO's attempting to determine outcomes by way of the heart and emotion, ignoring required logical practicalities. Try eating based purely on emotion....you'll be dead within a year. Are we now at the behest of organisations such as this? Is there any point in democracy anymore? As the old saying goes 'If you're not a liberal when young you have no heart, but if you're not a conservative when older, you have no Brain'.

66

Gerald Kelleher ^{1y}

Apr 15th 2024, 9:20 AM

It seems that the dynamics of society and what it registers as being important are misplaced. There is no climate change crisis as the Earth's climate is determined by the motions of the planet, so that leaves multiple research areas such as Ireland's maritime climate and the many inputs involved. The same goes for any other location on the planet.

There is a prejudice crisis, but the academic community that is intimately tied to the NGOs refuses to assert the only valid male/female distinctions as there are no 'races'.

It is society itself that has to change and sometimes that starts with the individual and a greater perceptive and reasoning balance.

36

N

Numinous20111^{2y}

Apr 15th 2024, 8:27 AM

Seems odd (yet again) that the same talking point is being repeated in several comments. Seems a bit like the latest tactic. Could someone please close that Overton window. There's a real dodgy whiff coming through it.....a far right tang.

39

P

Padraig O'Brien^{2y}

Apr 15th 2024, 10:02 AM

It's great isn't it how, when it suits, abhorace of NGOs can be conflated with abhorace of their client base.

Common with NGOs dealing with immigrants but not with NGOs dealing with domestic violence or cancer patients.

31

C

Conor Garvey^{2y}

Apr 15th 2024, 4:35 PM

The same oxfam who support dictators all all across the world

32

J

John Moore^{14y}

Apr 16th 2024, 12:28 AM

If somebody arrives with no documents why do we not have an agreement with the airlines on access to the record of the document they used to book the flight/board the plane. Surely that information could be easily provided and that whole problem solved in one go.

13

SV3tN8M41y

Apr 15th 2024, 11:56 PM

Maybe Jim will publish his salary & expenses & tell the public what percentage of funding is given to them by the State. Jim is not an elected official but seems to think he can dictate policy. NGO's & their CEO's all have an agenda & are beginning to grate on Taxpayers who have had enough of their crap.

Appendix G Social Constructivism

Social Constructivism

Ontological beliefs

- Multiple realities are constructed through our lived experiences and interactions with others

Epistemological beliefs

- Reality is constructed between the researcher and the researched and shaped by individuals' experiences

Axiological beliefs

- Individual values are honoured and are negotiated among individuals

Methodological beliefs

- More of a literary style of writing is used. Use of an inductive method of emergent ideas (through consensus) is obtained through methods such as interviewing, observing and analysing texts

Source: Adapted from Lincoln et al. (2011)

Table 2 Various interpretative frameworks and their associated philosophical beliefs

Interpretive Frameworks	Ontological Beliefs (the nature of reality)	Epistemological Beliefs (how reality is known)	Axiological Beliefs (role of values)	Methodological Beliefs (approach to inquiry)
Postpositivism	A single reality exists beyond ourselves, "out there." The researcher may not be able to understand it or get to it because of lack of absolutes.	Reality can only be approximated, but it is constructed through research and statistics. Interaction with research subjects is kept to a minimum. Validity comes from peers, not participants.	The researcher's biases need to be controlled and not expressed in a study.	Scientific method and writing is used. Object of research is to create new knowledge. Method is important. Deductive methods are important, such as testing of theories, specifying important variables, and making comparisons among groups.
Social constructivism	Multiple realities are constructed through our lived experiences and interactions with others.	Reality is co-constructed between the researcher and the researched and shaped by individual experiences.	Individual values are honored and are negotiated among individuals.	More of a literary style of writing is used. Use of an inductive method of emergent ideas (through consensus) is obtained through methods such as interviewing, observing, and analyzing texts.
Transformative/postmodern	Participation between researcher and communities or individuals is being studied. Often a subjective-objective reality emerges.	There are co-created findings with multiple ways of knowing.	There is respect for indigenous values; values need to be problematized and interrogated.	Methods consist of using collaborative processes of research, encouraging political participation, questioning of methods, and highlighting issues and concerns.
Pragmatism	Reality is what is useful, is practical, and "works."	Reality is known through using many tools of research that reflect both deductive (objective) evidence and inductive (subjective) evidence.	Values are discussed because of the way that knowledge reflects both the researchers' and the participants' views.	The research process involves both quantitative and qualitative approaches to data collection and analysis.
Critical, race, feminist, queer, disability	Reality is based on power and identity struggles. Privilege or oppression based on race or ethnicity, class, gender, mental abilities, sexual preference.	Reality is known through the study of social structures, freedom and oppression, power, and control. Reality can be changed through research.	Diversity of values is emphasized within the standpoint of various communities.	Start with assumptions of power and identity struggles, document them, and call for action and change.

Source: Adapted from Lincoln et al. (2011)

Appendix H

An open letter to negotiators in the European Commission, the Spanish Presidency of the Council of the European Union, and the European Parliament ahead of the final negotiations on the EU Pact on Migration

We are writing as concerned human rights defenders, and as people who see and work with the stark consequences of political choices.

The EU Pact on Migration and Asylum will mirror the failed approaches of the past and worsen their consequences. There is currently a major risk that the Pact results in an ill-functioning, costly, and cruel system that falls apart on implementation and leaves critical issues unaddressed.

If adopted in its current format, it will normalise the arbitrary use of immigration detention, including for children and families, increase racial profiling, use “crisis” procedures to enable pushbacks, and return individuals to so called "safe third countries" where they are at risk of violence, torture, and arbitrary imprisonment.

It also betrays the spirit of existing EU work, such as the EU Action Plan on Integration and the EU Action Plan Against Racism which recognises the intersectional impacts of racism and the specific vulnerability of migrants and refugees. The Pact, as it stands, risks perpetuating discriminatory practices within the very structures meant to uphold justice and protection for all.

We are acutely aware that politics is often about compromise. But there are exceptions, and human rights cannot be compromised. When they are weakened, there are consequences for all of us.

Rather than channelling funding towards more camps, walls, and surveillance, resources should go towards providing effective solutions, based on protection and assistance, of the kind offered to people fleeing Ukraine. Europe's solidarity and commitment to human rights cannot be defined by place of origin, race, ethnicity, or immigration status.

We should strengthen, not weaken, our reception and asylum systems and provide mechanisms to fairly share responsibility between European states. We need support for - not restrictions on - rescuing people at sea. We need more, not less, access to legal aid, asylum, medical and social support for people in need. We need real accountability for border forces that violate our laws. And we need more safe routes for people to move, work and settle in safety and dignity.

We have recently witnessed a dignified and compassionate response to displacement with the activation of the Temporary Protection Directive. This stands as a testament to the principles of human rights and protection that should guide our collective approach to these reforms. The New Pact must reflect and build upon this dignified response rather than leading Europe in the opposite direction.

There are times when political choices can make a profound difference, for better or for worse, to people's lives. Today is one such time. We're asking you to show leadership for the just and compassionate Europe we all want to live in.

Sincerely,

Joint statement: EU 'safe country' and return proposals would seriously undermine protection and human dignity

The EU's recent proposals in the area of migration and asylum risk seriously undermining people's access to fair and full asylum procedures in Europe. The European Commission's recent initiatives appear to be interconnected components of a broader strategy to externalise the bloc's migration management - these include its proposed revision to EU return or deportation rules put forward in March 2025, its April 2025 EU list of 'safe countries of origin' and a revision to the 'safe third country' concept in May 2025. With these measures the EU seems to be seeking to further shift responsibility for refugee protection onto countries outside its borders and sidestep legal obligations under the Refugee Convention and EU law.

EU List of 'Safe Countries of Origin'

The proposed EU list of 'safe countries of origin' deems certain countries, from which 20% or fewer applicants are granted international protection in the EU, to be safe. However, the fact that up to 20% of those applying for international protection from these countries are recognised as refugees indicates that these places are in fact *not* safe for all. Despite this, the proposed EU list allows for accelerated processing of asylum claims from nationals (or stateless individuals) of these countries under the assumption that their claims are likely to be unfounded.

As an aspect of the right to seek asylum, anyone who applies for protection in the EU should have their claim assessed individually and on its own merits - regardless of where they are fleeing from. The application of the 'safe country of origin' rule undermines the individual assessment of asylum claims and increases the risk of individual vulnerabilities and protection needs being missed – including those of people with specific needs or from marginalised communities by allowing for accelerated processing of asylum claims under the assumption that their claims are likely to be unfounded. Procedural safeguards are also limited in these accelerated procedures – meaning, for instance, shortened timeframes and limited access by the claimant to legal and other support.

The proposed 'safe countries of origin' are Egypt, Tunisia, Bangladesh, Colombia, India, Kosovo, and Morocco, as well as, in principle, EU candidate countries. This is deeply concerning given that the Explanatory Memorandum itself lists risks of violations of human rights in all countries listed in the Commission's proposal, ranging from widespread gender-based violence to severe threats human rights defenders face. As human rights organisations have noted, for example, Tunisian authorities intensified repression of political opposition in 2024 by carrying out mass arrests, imprisoning journalists, and targeting civil society groups. In Egypt, many peaceful critics and members of religious minorities face harassment and lengthy detention in dire conditions. Colombia remains one of the most dangerous countries in the world for individuals at risk of targeted violence, especially from non-state armed groups. Former combatants who signed the Peace Agreement, human rights defenders, community

leaders, environmental activists, and investigative journalists are frequently subjected to threats, attacks, persecution and killings. In addition, LGBTIQ+ individuals and ethnic minorities, including Afro-Colombian and Indigenous communities, face widespread discrimination, violence, and forced displacement. In Morocco, journalists, activists, and perceived government critics face harassment, arbitrary arrest and detention, and unfair trials. Other groups such as Sahrawi activists and LGBT+ individuals are also subjected to discrimination, surveillance, and prosecution.

This list of vulnerable groups in these third countries is non-exhaustive, and national asylum agencies across EU member states confirm that people from those countries remain in need of international protection, as their recognition rate has not lowered to zero.

Expansion of the ‘safe third country’ concept

A separate legislative proposal - the review of the ‘safe third country’ concept in the Asylum Procedures Regulation (which was introduced as part of the Migration and Asylum Pact and enters into force in 2026) - seeks to remove the current requirement for a personal connection between the asylum seeker and a third country where it is deemed they should have sought protection in the first place. Currently, the Regulation provides that Member States can avoid examining an asylum application on its merits only if it can be proven that the applicant has a meaningful connection to a ‘safe third country’.

The Commission's new proposal would effectively remove this mandatory criterion, paving the way for asylum seekers being sent to a country they have only briefly travelled through, or indeed have never set foot in and may have no link to whatsoever. Mere transit, or the existence of an agreement or ‘arrangement’ between an EU Member State and a third country would be considered sufficient grounds for an asylum seeker to be transferred to a country outside the EU.

The Commission proposal would also lead to the removal of the automatic suspensive effect of appeal in these cases. Therefore, asylum seekers could be forcibly transferred to a third country they have no link to before their appeal has been heard. This increases the risk of (chain) *refoulement* or of asylum seekers being unable to access their rights in line with the 1951 Refugee Convention and international human rights law. Dismantling this connection criterion is seemingly intended to increase the use of the ‘safe third country’ concept and further shift responsibility to third countries. This contradicts and harms the functioning of the EU asylum system and the global protection regime as whole.

Externalisation as the cross-cutting policy objective

The EU list of ‘safe countries of origin’ and proposed expanded use of ‘safe third country’ rules are clearly connected to the recently proposed Common European System for Returns. The proposed Return Regulation of March 2025 aims to streamline and expedite the return process for non-EU nationals denied permission to remain on EU territory. It includes a legal framework for establishing so-called ‘return hubs’ in third countries, where individuals issued final return orders may be forcibly sent and detained, based on agreements between a Member State and a third country. Human rights and humanitarian organisations have **warned** that these ‘return hubs’ risk resulting in human rights violations, arbitrary automatic detention, and both direct and indirect *refoulement*. The return proposal also vastly expands the number of countries to which returns can be carried out - including to the aforementioned ‘safe third countries’.

These different Commission proposals, taken together, reflect the EU's determination to further externalise its asylum and migration policy. This comes at the expense of focusing efforts on strengthening the capacity of national asylum systems, offering protection and welcoming people with dignity and respect. The EU's current approach undermines the rights of asylum seekers and migrants, and places undue responsibilities on third countries, some of which may already be hosting large communities of refugees and migrants.

Lessons have not been learned from existing migration agreements with non-EU countries, often those with poor human rights records, which have proved costly, cruel and counterproductive – such as with Türkiye, Libya, Tunisia or Egypt. Relying on third countries to take on Europe's protection obligations makes Europe dependent on non-EU states, enabling third countries to leverage migration in line with their own political agenda.

The EU's inability to effectively monitor and enforce human rights in partnerships with third countries has become increasingly evident, as reports of violations continue to mount. Shirking responsibility in this way has resulted in many thousands of people being exposed to violence, abuse, exploitation, and death. Rather than promoting solidarity, these policies appear to signal a retreat from Europe's commitment to asylum and risk contributing to a worrying erosion of refugee protection globally.

The undersigned organisations call on the European Commission, the European Parliament, the Council, and member states at national level to uphold their obligations under EU and international law and to firmly reject any attempts to weaken protection for asylum seekers at and within EU borders as well as in cooperation with third countries on asylum and migration.

Organisations signing on:

1. International Rescue Committee
2. Danish Refugee Council
3. Amnesty International
4. ILGA-Europe
5. Center for legal aid - Voice in Bulgaria
6. Iridia – Centre per la defensa dels drets humans
7. ActionAid International
8. Migration Consortium
9. Fenix Humanitarian Legal Aid
10. Defense for Children In. Greece (DCI - Greece)
11. ARSIS - Association for the Social Support of Youth
12. Mobile Info Team
13. EmpowerVan
14. WeMove Europe
15. Collective
16. Network for Children's Rights
17. Caritas Europa
18. Equal Legal Aid
19. Greek Forum of Refugees
20. Salud por Derecho
21. ARCI APS
22. Equinox Initiative for Racial Justice
23. Brussels Platform Armoede
24. FAIRWORK Belgium

25. CSC
26. Legal Centre Lesbos
27. CNCD-11.11.11
28. Centre Avec
29. Vluchtelingenwerk Vlaanderen
30. Greek Council for Refugees (GCR)
31. CIRÉ
32. Caritas International
33. Vluchtelingenwerk Vlaanderen vzw
34. I Have Rights
35. Boat Refugee Foundation
36. EuroMed Rights
37. LDH (Ligue des droits de l'Homme)
38. PICUM
39. Médecins du Monde
40. Safe Place Greece / International
41. Stichting Vluchteling
42. 11.11.11
43. The Swedish Network of Refugee Support Groups.
44. Churches' Commission for Migrants in Europe (CCME)
45. Brot für die Welt
46. Quaker Council for European Affairs
47. Progetto Sud ETS
48. Jesuit Refugee Service (JRS) Europe
49. SOLIDAR
50. Swedish Refugee Law Center
51. Human Rights Watch
52. HIAS Europe

Appendix I

Table A7. Pending cases at the end of the year in EU+ countries by reporting country and main citizenships, 2023-2024

					2024		
	2023	2024	Share in EU+	Change from 2023	First	Top three groups Second	Third
Spain	182,691	251,540	26%	▲ 38%	Colombia (35%)	Venezuela (34%)	Peru (8.9%)
Italy	162,091	227,127	23%	▲ 40%	Bangladesh (19%)	Pakistan (12%)	Egypt (11%)
Germany	239,614	212,656	22%	▼ -11%	Syria (23%)	Türkiye (21%)	Afghanistan (18%)
France	53,323	66,196	6.7%	▲ 24%	Guinea (10%)	Ukraine (9.3%)	Côte d'Ivoire (7.6%)
Netherlands	43,924	46,855	4.8%	▲ 7%	Syria (32%)	Türkiye (7.7%)	Iraq (7.5%)
Belgium	39,429	43,093	4.4%	▲ 9.3%	Palestine (14%)	Syria (11%)	Türkiye (8.3%)
Greece	29,885	26,623	2.7%	▼ -11%	Syria (28%)	Afghanistan (16%)	Egypt (15%)
Ireland	18,311	22,548	2.3%	▲ 23%	Nigeria (21%)	Jordan (10%)	Pakistan (7.9%)
Cyprus	26,599	20,652	2.1%	▼ -22%	Syria (67%)	Congo (DR) (8.8%)	Afghanistan (6.2%)
Austria	23,188	13,093	1.3%	▼ -44%	Syria (46%)	Afghanistan (15%)	Türkiye (10%)
Switzerland	15,567	11,921	1.2%	▼ -23%	Türkiye (33%)	Afghanistan (10%)	Iran (4.7%)
Poland	6,930	10,325	1.1%	▲ 49%	Ukraine (33%)	Russia (27%)	Belarus (19%)
Bulgaria	11,951	6,051	0.6%	▼ -49%	Syria (67%)	Afghanistan (21%)	Egypt (3.1%)
Norway	4,535	5,282	0.5%	▲ 16%	Syria (44%)	Ukraine (15%)	Türkiye (7.3%)
Finland	7,421	4,228	0.4%	▼ -43%	Somalia (15%)	Russia (15%)	Syria (8.8%)
Sweden	5,189	3,812	0.4%	▼ -27%	Syria (17%)	Afghanistan (7.6%)	Iran (6.8%)
Luxembourg	3,085	3,199	0.3%	▲ 4%	Syria (26%)	Entrea (20%)	Venezuela (6.6%)
Denmark	2,119	2,155	0.2%	➔ 2%	Ukraine (29%)	Syria (16%)	Türkiye (10%)
Croatia	1,538	1,120	0.1%	▼ -27%	Russia (28%)	Türkiye (12%)	Syria (11%)
Slovenia	1,147	850	0.1%	▼ -26%	Morocco (43%)	Ukraine (15%)	Algeria (6.9%)
Malta	832	507	0.1%	▼ -39%	Syria (23%)	Ukraine (18%)	Sudan (11%)
Latvia	591	221	0.0%	▼ -63%	Tajikistan (27%)	Afghanistan (21%)	Russia (11%)
Lithuania	346	219	0.0%	▼ -37%	Belarus (46%)	Russia (19%)	Ukraine (5.5%)
Romania	1,062	166	0.0%	▼ -84%	Syria (50%)	Iraq (21%)	Sudan (3.6%)
Estonia	354	148	0.0%	▼ -58%	Ukraine (67%)	Russia (16%)	Belarus (4.7%)
Portugal	363	129	0.0%	▼ -64%	Venezuela (18%)	China (17%)	Angola (12%)
Hungary	15	16	0.0%	▲ 7%	Nigeria (19%)	Uganda (13%)	Russia (13%)
Czechia	673	:					
Slovakia	:	:					
EU+	882,773	980,732	100.0%	▲ 11%	Syria (11%)	Colombia (9.9%)	Venezuela (9.4%)
Type of applicant					Countries of origin		
First time	652,234	688,564	70%	▲ 6%	Syria (15%)	Türkiye (9.2%)	Afghanistan (8%)
Unknown	195,661	257,810	26%	▲ 32%	Colombia (34%)	Venezuela (33%)	Peru (8.7%)
Repeated	33,311	32,829	3.3%	➔ -1.4%	Russia (12%)	Afghanistan (11%)	Syria (8.1%)
Relocated	1567	1529	0.2%	➔ -2%	Syria (16%)	Sudan (15%)	Afghanistan (14%)
Duration of pending					Countries of origin		
More than 6 months	436,992	639,194	65%	▲ 46%	Colombia (12%)	Venezuela (9.1%)	Syria (8.7%)
Less than 6 months	432,856	331,233	34%	▼ -23%	Syria (15%)	Venezuela (10%)	Afghanistan (7.2%)
Unknown	12,925	10,305	1.1%	▼ -20.3%	Syria (46%)	Afghanistan (16%)	Iran (2.8%)
Countries of origin					Reporting countries		
Syria	122,753	108,529	11%	▼ -12%	Germany (45%)	Netherlands (14%)	Cyprus (13%)
Colombia	76,673	97,160	9.9%	▲ 27%	Spain (90%)	Italy (4.9%)	Germany (1.9%)
Venezuela	58,621	92,606	9.4%	▲ 58%	Spain (92%)	Italy (3.6%)	Germany (2.3%)
Türkiye	83,964	66,098	6.7%	▼ -21.3%	Germany (67%)	Switzerland (6%)	Netherlands (5.5%)
Afghanistan	72,509	61,151	6.2%	▼ -16%	Germany (62%)	France (7%)	Greece (6.9%)
Bangladesh	32,946	47,778	4.9%	▲ 45%	Italy (89%)	France (5.6%)	Ireland (2.9%)
Peru	28,932	44,856	4.6%	▲ 55%	Spain (50%)	Italy (48%)	Germany (0.6%)
Pakistan	31,745	33,398	3.4%	▲ 5%	Italy (78%)	Ireland (5.3%)	Germany (4.6%)
Egypt	25,864	32,552	3.3%	▲ 26%	Italy (75%)	Greece (12%)	Germany (3.6%)
Eritrea	19,332	18,659	1.9%	▼ -3%	Italy (50%)	Netherlands (15%)	Germany (13%)
Other	329,434	377,945	39%	▲ 15%	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified

Notes: Data on pending cases were not available for Czechia and Slovakia for December 2024. Data of a magnitude of 5 or lower are rounded to the nearest multiple of 5. Thus, a 0 may not necessarily indicate a real zero value but could also represent a value of 1 or 2.

Map 4: The Hard Right in Europe

THE HARD RIGHT IN THE EU

In the countries shaded in light pink, hard-right* parties are in first or second place in the polls, according to POLITICO's Poll of Polls. In countries shaded in purple, these parties are either in government or part of the governing majority.

*Affiliated with either the European Conservatives and Reformists (ECR) or the Identity and Democracy (ID) groups in the European Parliament. Hungary is the exception to this rule: Viktor Orbán's Fidesz party quit the center-right European People's Party (EPP) group in 2021 amid criticism over his democratic record. Polling data as of May 23, 2024.

SOURCE: POLITICO research

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POLITICO

Endnotes

ⁱ The ‘New Community’ categorisation was collectively used in an Irish context to refer to someone who was an economic migrant, asylum seeker and/or a refugee from 2006-2023. In recent years the word *migrant* began to be increasingly included in EU policy documents and has been transported into the programme guidelines for Ireland’s only anti-poverty programme Social Inclusion and Community Activation Programme.

ⁱⁱ A tool applied to collate opinions from selected individuals followed up with focus groups.

ⁱⁱⁱ I consulted with ChatGPT to see an overview of past EU Asylum Policy for this area.

^{iv} History of the Common European Asylum System

Tampere Conclusions in 1999

Several rounds of reform of the CEAS

First: 1999

2003-2005

Second: 2006-2013

2016 – failed reform

Third: 2020 – New Pact on Migration and Asylum

Ireland participated in some but not all – CTA with UK.

Ireland has special opt-in under Protocol 21 to Lisbon Treaty.

First round

Temporary Protection Directive 2001/55

Eurodac Regulation 2725/2000

Dublin II Regulation 343/2003

Asylum Procedures Directive 2004/83

Qualification Directive 2004/83

Reception Conditions Directive 2003/9

Second round

Dublin III Regulation 604/2013

Eurodac Regulation

recast Asylum Procedures Directive 2013/32

recast Reception Conditions Directive 2013/33

recast Qualification Directive 2011/95

See: Cunliffe, E. (2025) The EU and Asylum Pact, Implications for Ireland, School of Law Trinity College.

^v Ireland officially opted into the Pact on June 27, 2024, following a vote in both houses of the Oireachtas. While the Pact is legally in effect, Ireland, along with other EU countries, has until June 12, 2026, to fully implement the new regulations.

^{vi} A person who is not a citizen of the European Union (EU) within the meaning of Article 20(1) TFEU and who is not a person enjoying the EU right of free movement as defined in Article 2(5) of the Schengen Borders Code. Nationals of Norway, Iceland, Liechtenstein and Switzerland are not considered to be third country nationals (European Migration Network, V6).

^{vii} A person who, owing to irregular entry, breach of a condition of entry or the expiration of their legal basis for entering and residing, lacks legal status in a transit or host country. The term undocumented migrant is also used (European Migration Network, V6).

^{viii} Sweeney outlines that Ireland will be required to transpose eight legislative acts (Table 1) into domestic legislation and to repeal the International Protection Act 2015 between now and July 2026, which will be overseen by an interdepartmental board. Several key challenges exist from an Irish perspective, namely, the Asylum

Procedure Regulation (APR), Asylum Migration Management Regulation, and the Recast Eurodac Regulations for day-to-day operations. Under the Pact, inadmissibility decisions should occur with two months and that under a new border procedure first instance, appeal and return decisions should occur within three months.

^{ix} Despite the growing body of scientific evidence concerning the extent and impacts of climate change, meaningful policy responses have not been forthcoming” (Pringle & Robbins, 2022: p. 59). The Earth’s surface is now 1.17°C or 2.11°F warmer than in the 1880’s and warmer than any time over the past 100,000 years. The consequences of climate change are resulting in the melting of the world’s glaciers and ice sheets, flooding, longer droughts, crop failures, ever more violent storms, and declining biodiversity (NASA, 2024). The scale of the challenge for humanity is enormous in responding to *climate change*.

^x Article 14 provides a legal right to seek asylum in another country due to persecution.

^{xi} The EU itself is an international treaty composed of five institutions. There are two competing tendencies at its core, one that has a community dynamic with a federal vocation and another with “intergovernmental cooperation in foreign and internal policies” (Sidjanski, p.1). As such, a game of tug and war between countries and EU institutions who favour further integration on social policy issues and those who are more reluctant to do so. Critically, foreign affairs and security policy are still the preserve of member states, and the new Pact has led to the formulation of a misconceived vision around a ‘Fortress Europe’.

^{xii} European Fisheries Control Agency, European Maritime Safety Agency, European Union Aviation Safety Agency, European Union’s Judicial Cooperation Unit, European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation, European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Training and European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights.

^{xiii} Original French language version: <http://libertaire.free.fr/MFoucault162.html>

^{xiv} In part, the EU Charter resembles the Universal Declaration of Human Rights with fifty-four articles under different thematic areas. Article 1, listed under the heading of *dignity* states that “Human dignity is inviolable. It must be respected and protected”. Elsewhere, Article 18 under the heading of *freedom* extends to the right to “the right to asylum shall be guaranteed with due respect for the rules of the Geneva Convention of 28 July 1951 and the Protocol of 31 January 1967 relating to the status of refugees and in accordance with the Treaty establishing the European Community. Finally, Article 19 concerns protection in the event of removal, expulsion, or extradition. It states that “collective expulsions are prohibited and that no one may be removed, expelled or extradited to a State where there is a serious risk that he or she would be subjected to the death penalty, torture or other inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.

^{xv} In a strict sense there is no such thing as QR. There is no single practice, perspective attitude about data, or approach to social science that all scholars who have used that term to describe their work follow...one way of making sense of this heterogeneity is to understand that Q can refer to at least three elements of the research project. The type of data, the method of data collection, or the approach to data analysis (Conzon and Small, 2022, pp9).

^{xvi} The first couple of questions were designed to enable international and national networks who defend asylum seekers to demonstrate the arduous journeys they often undertake and the barriers they might typically experience in having their applications accessed and possibly after they are granted asylum and eventual refugee status: (1) Could you tell me about the types of journeys people fleeing persecution have to undertake to reach Europe? (2) Could you tell me about the barriers they face in claiming asylum and gaining refugee status within the EU?.

Questions three to seven were more political in character and deemed essential given that the Pact is International in its application across EU Member States. All the organisations that were on my potential list of respondents had an opportunity to submit their views to the European Commission’s Migration Home Affairs Directorate General before the Pact was signed off on by the Council in December 2023. They also lobby the European Parliament in Strasbourg and the Committees who MEPs are members of (and their own national parliament 3. Could you discuss the policy submissions your organisation has submitted to the Institutions of the European Union in advance of the signing off of the EU asylum and migration pact?: (4) In what way has the changing nature of the political representation of the European Parliament changed the debate and final version of the EU asylum and migration pact? (5) What would you see are the potential strengths of the EU asylum and migration pact? (6) What would you see are the potential weaknesses of the EU asylum and migration pact?.

Questions seven and eight were inserted to try and source insightful information as how some of the root causes of asylum can be minimised to inform my Policy Chapter. Question nine attempted to elicit feedback around if the Pact was in keeping with the values of social justice and the final question provided the opportunity for the respondent to talk ad lib and provide additional information that might have been overlooked during the interview. (8) How does that differ from your approach as an organisation if at all? (9) On reflection, do you think that the EU asylum and migration pact is in accordance with international human rights and the values of social justice? (10) Finally, is there anything else you would like to add or other important aspects I might have forgotten to question you about?

^{xvii} Unfortunately, it proved impossible to interview people by phone, in-person or via Zoom with the exception of one person

^{xviii} *I arrived in the UK when I was 23. I had nothing – no friends, no family, no home. Thankfully, I found the church, who took me in as one of their own. Now, when someone uses the term ‘family’, I think about my church family. For a while, I felt like life was improving. But then my asylum claim was refused by the Home Office and I was detained. I spent almost two months in detention. Alone in my cell, I stayed awake at night and slept during the day. I was depressed, undead. In detention, my flashbacks and nightmares grew worse. Eventually, I was released from detention, but the psychological damage was already done. It was at this stage that I attempted to take my own life (Mouhamed).*

^{xix} I live in constant fear of being arrested at any moment, fear of being deported to a country where I am no longer safe. I have no one to confide in and I don't dare to seek official help because I fear it will make my situation worse. My only hope is that one day I can live here without having to flee or hide. (40-year-old man from Guinea Conakry, interviewed in Brussels)

^{xx} I have anonymised the names of the five people who responded to the online questionnaire and the individual took part in a telephone interview. Four of these completed data consent forms that I can prove if necessary to SETU but two others did not despite follow up emails.

^{xxi} *Hold on, he is complaining about. People who have travelled on false documents will be put in detention while their application is being processed. What's the problem? That's exactly what should happen. If I went to another country on a false document, I'd be put in jail. That's the problem with these NGOs, they are so out of touch with reality that they think certain laws shouldn't apply to them. (Shane Kinsella)*

Nonsense. Ireland trades with nearly every country in the world, including such human rights luminaries as North Korea, China & Saudi Arabia. You can freely travel to China or Saudi Arabia for your holidays, but what is safe for you is not necessarily safe for a Chinese or Saudi Arabian national seeking asylum in Ireland. I could come up with multiple more examples, but I suggest you do your own research – you might learn something (Kevin Kerr)

^{xxii} A note of caution should be aired about the results of IPSOS survey in that people were asked about *irregular* migration and not migration that can naturally occur within the EU given that the free movement of person's is enshrined in Treaties. Nevertheless, the findings of the survey administered three months before the election, provided ammunition to centre right political parties such as the European People's Party to lobby the EU Institutions in the run up to elections about the future shape of the Pact. The Mixed Migration Centres research provides a more holistic impression around attitudes to migration.

^{xxiii} Horwood a migration specialist reasons that measuring public attitudes to matters including migration can differ radically depending on the approach taken. Very often they apply Likert type scales such as “agree/disagree” and “user/no”. More recently, researchers are also using social listening tools and “sentiment analysis algorithms”. Irrespective of what approach is taken they all have their limitations.

^{xxiv} Advent of Artificial Intelligence: In the run up to the European elections in 2024, Artificial Intelligence was used by far-right groups to spread propaganda on social media networks. The German far-right *Alternative für Deutschland* took out advertising space on FACEBOOK showing an image of a blonde hair and blue-eyed woman holding a German flag contrasted with a veiled woman and someone else holding a rainbow-coloured flag. Similar outwardly racist images were uploaded by parties in other countries such as Lege in Italy who published fake images of a bearded pregnant man alongside men in traditional Arab clothing burning Dante's Divine Comedy.

What we are seeing is the tip of the iceberg because what is coming from individuals and beyond the official channels is even worse (Salvatore Romano, head of research at the non-profit AI Forensics).

Appealing to a political fringe that had shown an attitude of "pragmatic opportunism" to new technology AI lowers the barriers to entry for creating content. You don't need coding skills or anything like that to generate these images. It is also symptomatic of far-right views going mainstream or being normalised (William Allchorn, Senior Research Fellow at Anglia Ruskin University)

Geo-political changes: There has been a general shift towards far-right parties in European politics. Italy, Finland, Slovakia, Hungary, Croatia, and Czechia now all have far right parties in government. In the European elections held in June 2024, no single political bloc emerged dominant. Nevertheless, the far right has made inroads in shaping the EU Asylum and Migration Pact. Ursula von der Leyen who was re-elected as president of the European Commission in July 2024 made overtures "to the hard-right ECR, led by Giorgia Meloni's Brothers of Italy and Poland's Law and Justice" (Euronews, online: 2024). In the run up to the European elections she professed that:

We all understand this fundamental truth. Migration is a European challenge which must be met with a European solution. One that is effective, and both fair and firm. This is what the Pact on Migration and Asylum delivers. It will be making a real difference for all Europeans (Ursula von der Leyen, European Commission President, 10 April 2024)

More worrying, is that she has also asked EU leaders to explore *return hubs* akin to the Italy-Albania deal as a potential model for other countries to follow. However, in an apparent blow to the aspirations of the Italian government and the EU Commission President, the Italian judiciary has twice rejected Giorgia Meloni's hubs and requested that the EU's top court examine the legality of the actual programme (Financial Times, 2024). Undeterred, the Italian government signed a decree to use these Albanian migration centres as repatriation hubs that will fast track asylum processing (Euronews, 2025). This has occurred before the European Court of Human Rights makes a ruling about such centres.

^{xxv} The European Commission has recently unveiled plans to spend a €2 trillion budget from 2028-2032 that must be adopted by the European Union through the interaction of the various institutions. €9.88 billion post 2027 is to be allocated to the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund

^{xxvi} Algeria is now deemed to be a 'safe country' under asylum rules in Ireland despite the security status stated on the Department of Foreign Affairs website as of [15-8-25] stating that, its security status is a 'High Degree of Caution'. Further to this, under local laws and customs it states that "Homosexuality is illegal in Algeria. Sexual acts between people of the same sex are punishable by imprisonment and homophobic attacks can take place. Caution and discretion are advised at all times".

^{xxvii} Appeals are running at eighty per cent in Ireland and approximately one-third of appeals are successful at the International Protection Appeals Tribunal. At face value, this high percentage of decisions being overturned by the International Protection Appeals Tribunal suggests too many errors are taking place at first instance. (RTE, 2025). Please click here to listen to <https://www.rte.ie/radio/radio1/clips/22500352/>

^{xxviii} <https://euaa.europa.eu/asylum-report-2020/713-return-former-applicants>

^{xxix} The UN Committee on the Rights of the Child issued disquiet about how several EU countries were determining a person's age (ECRE, 2022 and EUAA, 2023).

^{xxx} Head 12 of the new General Scheme of the International Protection Bill 2025 has granted significant new powers to An Garda Síochána to detain children without a warrant with no limit on their detention.

^{xxxvi} The recent analysis from the UN indicates that methane contributes 84 to 86 times more to global warming per unit of mass than carbon dioxide during the first twenty years (United Nations Environmental Programme, 2021). The leading greenhouse gases that are causing climate change include carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O). The main sectors of the economy that are causing greenhouse gases include transport, energy, industry, agriculture, and land use. (United Nations, 2024). The Gaia hypothesis conceives that the Earth and its biological systems operate as a single entity and therefore change in one area influences change in another (Science Direct, 2024). Methane has a very different warming impact than carbon dioxide, due to its higher global warming potential.

^{xxxvii} Irish news coverage too often only shows RTE reports outside of IPA centres where protests occur or of images of tents by the side of the Grand Canal.

^{xxxviii} A citizen's initiative *#RegulizationYa* signed by 600,000 people and supported by NGO's has led to a Spanish Parliament debate about the regularisation of over half-a-million undocumented foreigners living in Spain. 310 votes out of 343 supported the legislative process (Heller, 2024).

^{xxxix} My analysis chapter highlighted how gender-based violence is an enormous issue for women and girls who have been displaced and forced to seek asylum.

^{xl} Religious persecution has forced many people to seek asylum as highlighted in the analysis chapter.

^{xli} The welfare states of many EU countries will simply collapse without immigration or unless there is a sudden increase in the birth rates over an extended time period to 2.1 and over.

^{xlii} The EU will not be acting towards people fleeing climate change disasters in the 'spirit of brotherhood' as Article 1 of the UNHR Charter demands. Article 9 also clearly outlines that no one shall be subject to arbitrary arrest, detention or exile. It is legitimate to ask if a response to a social policy issue is premeditated, can it be considered arbitrary in the context of UNHR Charter. Do human rights matter after all? The principle of *non-Refoulement* is supposedly an absolute prohibition. How these procedures and rules interface with Articles 18/19 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and Article 33 of the 1951 Refugee Convention, may yet be decided on by the European Court of Human Rights in the future.

^{xliiii} *Instead of standing in a public square and saying that you think and then letting people come and listen to you and have that shared experience of what your narrative is, you're whispering into the ear of each and every voter and you maybe whispering one thing to one voter and another thing to another voter. We risk fragmenting society in a sense that we don't have shared experiences, and we don't have any more shared understanding. If we don't have any more shared understanding, how can we be as a functioning society. If you want to fundamentally change society, you first have to break it and it's only when you break it that you can remould the pieces* (Whistleblower, Christopher Wylie)

^{xliiii} Such a concept first mooted by the Conservative Party in the UK was rejected by the British Supreme Court and later abandoned by the new British Prime Minister (Frances, 2024).